

ACADEMIC RESEARCH RESPONSIVENESS TO 'ETHNIC MINORITIES' AND 'MIGRANTS' IN NORTHERN IRELAND

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Migration, race and ethnicity, majority-minority dynamics are established areas of academic enquiry in many contexts around the world. While that may be the case, in one devolved region of the United Kingdom (UK), that of Northern Ireland (NI), these are significantly under-studied when it comes to local populations and issues. This study sought to comprehend how such localised research enquiry is constructed, perceived and impacted by the various stakeholders who influence that contexts' higher education ecology.

SOURCES AND METHODS

A mixed method, exploratory approach was taken.

i. **Critical analysis of research output:**

Collated from over 120K recorded research items of the NI research-intensive universities, were 209 research outputs (from 159 projects) that were about local social groups of 'ethnic minorities' or 'migrants' in NI.¹ It was found that the first was published in 1994, and as such the range of outputs included were 1994-2022. These were analysed, and mapped in terms of authorship; disciplines; focal topics; methodological approach, including data sources, methods, ethics and positionality; funding; whether outputs included impact-related recommendations, and/or recommendations for research.

ii. **Participating authors:**

Of the 247 authors of the above items, 32 elected to participate in either interviews or via questionnaires. The questions that were posed about such research, elicited responses about the private gains and intentionality; experiences of the stop-starts of the research lifecycle; and their reflections of the particular enablements and constraints for such research and its impact within NI.

iii. **Responses of institutional practitioners and non-academic partners:**

Of the 12 individuals contacted within the research development offices of the NI institutions, 2 elected to participate in report-and respond discussions. Of the 14 partner organisations named within the research outputs, 3 members of a non-governmental organisation elected to respond to patterns from the critical literature review, adding reflections from their perspectives.

¹ Refer to Appendix A for information about the nomenclature 'ethnic minority' and 'migrant' in this report.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Particular findings are highlighted here. Please refer to the full report for more detail and nuance.

1. RESEARCH-INTENSIVE UNIVERSITIES ARE NOT RESPONSIVE TO CHANGES IN LOCAL SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHICS

The study found that Northern Ireland's research-intensive institutions are not responding to the changes in their local populations through their research function. Recorded on the institutions' Research Information Management Systems were 209 outputs related to this area of enquiry; compared to over 120 000 recorded outputs on other subjects. This lack of engagement, effectively under-serves and maintains the historical un-documenting of the histories, perspectives, needs and accounts of ethnic minorities and migrants through academic knowledge production. Localised knowledges and perceptions about such minoritised groups are left open to continued nonhistorical, decontextualised, unsupported, nonfactual, invented or imagined assumptions, stereotyping, othering and homogenising. Such under-responsiveness places the burden of knowledge-making on non-academic individuals or groups; or those academics positioned outside of the locality.

2. GROWTH IN THE POST-CONFLICT PERIOD IS PRESENT, BUT SCHOLARLY ENQUIRY IS MARGINAL

There was marked growth in academic research about this area of enquiry. The outputs recorded on the institutional Research Information Management Systems (RIMS) were from 1994, with increases until the peak year of engagement in 2018, following which it seems to have dropped somewhat. However, at no given year were there ever as many as 25 outputs (including academic dissemination, and translation outputs) produced on this area in NI. Less than half the research outputs were for academic dissemination. Thus, the field cannot be said to be established within this context.

3. INVESTMENT IS NEEDED FOR THIS AREA OF ENQUIRY TO GROW AND BECOME SUSTAINABLE

Triangulated data from this study, indicated that much more investment would be needed to make this a sustainable area of local enquiry. This includes both financial investment (by external funders and institutions improving their internal calls), in addition to research development (by institutions and by academics within them) and improving the research-teaching nexus. A central concern is to increase the capacity of those who are ethnic minorities to author academic knowledge, and thus recruitment and academic appointments would be an area of investment.

The SLR revealed that under 40% of the projects received partial or full funding. Most of the funding was by non-academic funders (with reports and journal articles), then academic funders (predominantly producing journal articles) or bodies connected to

the NI government (predominantly producing reports). Funding by non-academic organisations and by the NI government produced the most outputs. 10 projects were funded by non-UK funding, and only one by UK government funding.

The mapping of research lifecycles indicated high levels of investment by the researchers to bridge funding gaps, which often disenchanted those who tried and then abandoned the area after the experience of one project. Funding was described as limited and limiting of inclusive practice. There was often expectation of a high production of non-academic outputs for impact, without the necessary funding to capacitate that fully.

4. PARTICIPATION: POSITIONING AND AUTHORSHIP

The study found that there was a high proportion of the outputs that included the participation of the people under study (who inputted into primary data generation), almost as much as those projects where they were the subject of study. This is a positive indication. However, non-academic partner organisations were rarely named or acknowledged within the output.

Intersecting systems of discrimination impacted academic authorship in this area of enquiry; despite the subject matter being about ethnic minorities. The lead author position was rarely a person racialised as other-than-'white', and particularly not a woman racialised as other-than-'white' nor a person born locally.

A positive finding was that the majority of authors of these outputs were women and/or migrants, with far more representation than their populations within the staff compositions of NI universities. Thus representation, participation and authorship are not as yet democratic in this context.

5. ACADEMIC AUTHORS: WRITING BETWEEN AND ACROSS THE LINES

Many of the participating authors were cognisant about how they utilised their agency to negotiate different audiences during the research lifecycle. They negotiated tensions between the pragmatism of efficiency and the ideals of the ethical. This was raised in relation to communication with audiences who had power to provide funding (thus at proposal stage), and those who had power to lead or implement change (impact) which in almost all cases were understood to be members of the majority groups who often utilised deficit discourses and incorrect or problematic terminology. In rare cases, particularly experienced by those few authors who had been undertaking the research for a longer time, the length of relationships had to some extent informed and improved the assumptions, expectations, discourses and relations with practitioner audiences. Some authors admitted that much of what they produced was common knowledge to the participants anyway - the role of the output was the authorising of such claims. Participating authors also highlighted challenges when representing knowledge about NI to international audiences.

6. THE FUNCTION OF ACADEMIC KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION WAS INFORMED BY THE TECHNOCRATIC, SECTARIAN, RACIALISED CONTEXT

The publication of academic research was found to serve a number of dominant pre-defined functions within Northern Ireland; and these determined the ways in which the subject and related sociodemographic groups were constructed in the research process and represented in the outputs. It also impacted the methods of output, and the constructions of the authors. There was an avoidance of complexity of topics and insights, and of transparency in the methodological and ethical deliberations of the authors.

Thus, while the existing outputs have within them much value and have in some cases been lauded and appreciated by the studied groups, the research ecology was found to adversely impact academic autonomy and limit academic development. The politics of knowledge production in this area and of authorship involves fraught conditions internal to the institutions, and to wider public in the external NI research ecology, which reduce the potential of such research to contribute to academic knowledge; as rich, intersectional documentation of minoritized and racialised groups, and of the rapidly changing context; and also erode its potential impact on social change.

RECOMMENDATIONS

FOR FUTURE RESEARCH FUNDING:

- A diversity of interests and topics in fundings calls
- Plural types of research, with a strengthening of that which is societal need and challenge-led to be interdisciplinary; and more research that aims to document and to contribute to academic knowledge
- Projects which go into more depth within specific groups, rather than homogenising people by nationality, racialisation or their 'otherness' to dominant local 'communities'
- The participation of all research participants (sources, advisory boards, partners, researchers) should be acknowledged and reimbursed appropriately

FOR RESEARCH-INTENSIVE INSTITUTIONS:

- Connect employment practices with research development to address the lack of a pipeline from local ethnic minorities to knowledge production and intellectual leadership; and to reward research productivity in this area in promotion and awards
- Invest in responsiveness to these publics within your locality, including internal calls and scholarships
- Develop guidelines for authorship, attribution and acknowledgement in research with participants that are unrecognised in their local contexts, including that of NI

FOR RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT:

- Tailor funding calls for research with this local population
- Support network building and seed funding between local researchers across discipline and institutions in NI, and extending internationally in cognate areas
- Promote consciousness raising for academics researching all NI communities on the implications of exclusion and omission
- Invest in research development opportunities for growing this research area
- Reward and recognize those with a track record in this area

FOR AUTHORS:

- Network with local and international researchers in this area to strengthen skills, resilience, street smarts and self-reflexivity, and to increase collaboration for competitiveness in funding
- Deliberate the efficacy versus integrity conundrum as a research community

FOR IMPACTED GROUPS AND NGOS:

- Where possible, consider and assert acknowledgement of your involvement in research
- Exploit open access availability to read the research outputs of those who approach you, or whom you approach, to assess research integrity
- Consider the politics of authorship and how to support the authoring of knowledge from those with experience or sustained commitments to local issues
- Call for national oversight of equality reporting and monitoring across the academic pipeline - to address inequalities in local ethnic minorities' access to undergraduate higher education, through postgraduate studies, to academic staff composition and progression.

INTRODUCTION TO THE PROJECT ON ACADEMIC RESPONSIVENESS IN NORTHERN IRELAND

Migration, race and ethnicity, majority-minority dynamics are established areas of academic enquiry in many contexts around the world. However, these local dynamics have remained under-studied within academic enquiry in Northern Ireland, despite significant local socio-demographic change in the past three decades.

Northern Ireland (NI) is one of the four devolved nations of the United Kingdom (UK). At the time of writing, it shared an open, but racialised (Kramer et al., 2018), border with the Republic of Ireland. NI often falls within descriptions of a context that is High-Income and mono-ethnic, -lingual and -religious. Indeed, when classified according to state categorisations of social groups in NI, the majority of the population could be described as homogenous in terms of being overwhelmingly of 'white' ethnicity/ race, English-speaking, and of 'Christian' background and religious belief. However, it is also a region that has had continual ethnopolitical divisions for hundreds of years, (re)asserted through political, educational, religious, economic and familial structures. The legacies of these continue in the struggles for control over resources, rights, identities, and governance. Considerable research has been undertaken during the current post-conflict period about, and with, the dominant populations of Northern Ireland, including historic and current dynamics, concerns and perspectives. The universities are anchor universities, in that they focus much of their investment in research, teaching, third mission activities and public relations on the dominant populations of Northern Ireland, and in particular the city of Belfast. Thus, Northern Ireland claims to be a region with an active research culture about local and international populations and subjects. The responsiveness of its universities to the majority populations, and to international enquiry about migration, ethnicity/ race and majority-minority dynamics, is thus not the subject of this study.

Parallel to this dominant focus, is a peculiar lack of prioritisation of certain local populations, topics, histories and problems in Northern Ireland – that of local 'ethnic minorities' and 'migrants'.² Encapsulated in these oft-used impoverishing terms are those whose ancestries, ethnicities, nationalities, racialisation, languages, religions and belief systems, access and participation within Northern Ireland are either categorised (by the state or the dominant ingroups) or self-identified as 'different to' or 'other' than the norms of the dominant in-groups.

² Please refer to Appendix A for the problematics with such classifications; and the approach to nomenclature adopted within this report.

The study specifically explored academic research production: analysing what had been produced, and engaging with the authors thereof, in a bid to comprehend the conditions for marginalised academic enquiry.

Academic research offers potential to create knowledge, to author insights of depth and complexity, to witness time- and space-specific phenomena. It holds power, in that the knowledge it creates is legitimised within academia and peer reviewed publications as worthy of reproduction across academic communities, including to those learning and forming their sense of self in relation to the world. It is increasingly being used to provide an evidence-base to prove efficacy, to inform decision-making, and on which to base advocacy. As figures, academic citizens who conduct research are globally understood as having validated expertise, integrity and skills that place them in a trusted and privileged position to undertake research and represent it in ethical and responsible ways. The supports to practice such academic freedoms should be provided by institutional conditions that ensure their academic autonomy. Implicit within such value and expectations, are the politics of representation and authority about academic knowledge production and authorship. These have global dimensions of the university; however, there are contextual socio-cultural constructions. Moreover, the politics of responsiveness differs according to context too, since that is a discourse that has emerged to satisfy critiques of the ivory tower's elitism and distance from local concerns. In the UK generally, the 'public good' has become co-opted to demonstrating taxpayers' returns on their investments in public institutions, rather than democratisation, social justice or truth. Moreover, who falls within the 'public' can become a politicised debate within a contexts where divided groups are often in competition for attention.

Setting the context

While universities are international in many respects, the specific context within which institutions, academic authors and research participants are situated impacts on research practices. Not only are contextual influences of importance for analysing the practices of those primary actors, they also have direct relation to many of the intended readers of the 'pathways to impact' of the research (such as policy makers, lobbyists, politicians and non-academic practitioners). Perceptions about the context also affect research bureaucracy, including those who enable such research (including funders and universities); peer reviewers (of funding applications, ethics review boards and publications) and international collaborators. Moreover, in the case of research focused on domestic matters and populations, the context has a direct relation on those to whom the scholarship refers.

This section will not attempt an holistic analysis of the context as a whole, but rather will briefly contextualise aspects of relevance to migration and non-majoritarian ethnicity in NI. For a fuller picture, please refer the literature in the dataset itself.

Northern Ireland

Historical record of those of the non-dominant populations in NI has large gaps. Mirroring its governmental discourse, Northern Ireland Census excluded ethnic identification or race as a category for the reporting of its populations until 2001 (Crangle, 2018; Watson & McKnight, 1998). The inadequate structures and systems in place for ethnic monitoring disallow identifying the numbers or complexities of ethnicity and of migration, and for predicting future patterns of relations, departure and arrival (McAreavey, 2012). It is primarily in oral history and press archives where there are insights into the richness of the migration, settling, exchange and footprint of various people well before, and during, the 1900's. This includes the indigenous ethnic minority groups known as The Travellers. People of various faiths have been present for hundreds of years in NI, some with organised religious infrastructure. Undoubtedly though, increases in variety and numbers have been more prevalent since late 1998, in the so-called post-conflict period.

Minority ethnic inhabitants may have been considered invisible in Northern Ireland during the 1900's, yet they experienced some of the most restrictive legislation in the UK due to intense concern about cross-border infiltration (Crangle, 2018; Murphy & Vieten, 2017) which continues today in the form of the racialised Irish border (Kramer et al., 2018) and the UK's various iterations of the hostile environment. During the period of 'home rule', foreigners faced considerable difficulties in gaining access to employment in Northern Ireland due to barriers imposed by the Safeguarding of Employment Act (Northern Ireland, 1947). This was only repealed in 1977 when NI was under 'direct rule' of Westminster (Crangle, 2023). This is but one example of how legislation, designed to restrict the rights of local Catholic populations and the access of those from the Republic of Ireland, impacted on migration. However, even during that period, those from countries with links to the British Empire did gain entry. That included groups of those impacted by the partition of India and Pakistan in 1947, and people of Chinese-origin or descent in the 1960s. Both have since prospered as 'communities' within NI. African academic citizens studied, and returned, during this period too (Morier-Genoud, 2021). Documented experiences of those from Indian and Chinese communities record how minority ethnic populations in Northern Ireland in the twentieth century suffered both 'explicit and covert' race-based discrimination and injustices throughout the 20th Century (Crangle, 2018, p. 31). These were publicly known, and in some cases even perpetrated by high ranking officials but were not punishable by law.

NI has a peculiar relation to the question of racism in its midst. Political discourse by those in governance in NI has most often expressed denial of race-based discrimination and been dismissive of approaches for related social regulation. As with many settler colonies, this pattern which was established by the British Empire did not shift under 'home rule', nor during the initial global decolonisation periods of the 1960s. It was later out of step with legislation in the rest of the UK, when under 'direct rule' of Westminster during the period of conflict. This pattern persists in the present day of it being a 'devolved nation' of the UK, where policy implementation is yet to occur and

the public is grossly unaware of such policy's existence (Northern Ireland Life & Times Survey, 2022).

Tracing the question of race

Crangle (2018) writes about how, when in 1965 the Race Relations Act was passed across regions of the UK except for Northern Ireland, NI officials were uncharacteristically in unanimous agreement that it was unnecessary for the local context. Across the political divides, there was both a denial of any race-related problems in Northern Ireland and assertions that people racialised as other-than-'white' were respected in NI. Several of the Race Relations Bills proposed to the House of Commons were refused. Northern Ireland officials and politicians continued to dismiss the possibility of racism in Northern Ireland. Indications are that such resistance to social regulation not only limited NI's stance to addressing sectarianism, colour-based racism and religious discrimination, it also played a role in shaping legislation across the UK too, at least initially, when the NI government "secretly, and successfully, lobbied to restrict the terms of the UK's first Race Relations Act" (Gilligan, 2022, p. 13).

The rejection of the Race Relations Act in NI did not generate substantial public local or international controversy at the time. This lack of attention continued until 1978, when external observers from the international community of the Committee for Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD) noted the uneven implementation of the Race Relations Act across the UK. Nevertheless, the criticism from the CERD conference did not lead to any significant change. By the mid-1990s, when minorities in the rest of the UK had been protected by law for thirty years, Northern Ireland was still not committed to providing protections against discrimination nor promoting race relations. The British Race Relations was passed in 1965, 1968, and 1976; however, Northern Ireland during the Troubles was exempted as a supposedly mono-ethnic society and, despite the end of violence, has not yet sufficiently caught up with race-related legislation in the rest of the UK.

The 'Troubles' period

Civil conflict, violence and military operations during the internationally publicised period which has become known as 'The Troubles' (1968-1998) characterized the region as unstable, dangerous, and hostile. The extent of such activity is not comparable to the higher death toll and brutality of many other conflicts, before and since that period. However, the perception of instability is frequently cited to explain low immigration levels during that period. Even during this period there were pockets of migration, including groups of those from Portugal and Zimbabwe. It was particularly the treatment of racialised minorities as subordinate to the predominant concern with sectarian politics, that left issues such as barriers to migration, integration, discrimination and various other 'race relations' considerations overlooked in policy and public discourse (Crangle, 2023; Hainsworth, 1998; G. Irwin & Dunn, 1997).

The Post-conflict period

Following the Northern Ireland peace agreement in 1998, post-conflict Northern Ireland witnessed a drastic increase in migrant and minority populations. Sociodemographic changes which occurred during the devolved nation's 'post-conflict' period have included increases in those foreign-born, from 1.09% to 6.53%, and in those racialised as other-than the 'white' majority, from 0.8% to 3.4% (according to Census data of 1991 and 2021). Even though there has been a doubling in the population of those categorised as 'ethnic minorities' from 32,400 in the 2011 Census to 65,000 in the 2021 census (NISRA, 2022d), to date, Northern Ireland remains the least ethnically diverse region of the United Kingdom. Changes in religion have included an increase in those with religion other-than-Christian, from 0.4% in 2001 to 1.5% in 2021, and an increase over the same period of those without religion, from 2.7% to 9.3% (NISRA, 2022c). Increases in languages other than English, Irish or Ulster Scots were also recorded, from 3.1% in 2011 to 4.6% in 2021 (NISRA, 2022b). However, over 25 years later, racial equality strategies and policies in post-conflict Northern Ireland are yet to match the needs of the new publics.

Equality struggles characterised the peace-process. However, it took the struggles of minority ethnic groups to push Northern Ireland to finally pass the Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order (RRO) in 1997 and the Northern Ireland Act in 1998. Notably, Section 75 of the Good Friday Agreement (1998) specifies that public authorities have a duty to promote equality of opportunity and provide protections in relation to nine categories, including 'racial group' and 'religious belief'. A new body - The Equality Commission - was formulated at that time to replace four bodies (the Fair Employment Commission, the Equal Opportunities Commission, the Commission for Racial Equality and the Disability Council), and to "maintain the powers of all the [related] anti-discrimination legislation" (BBC NI, n.d.). Evident in the list below, is that race, discrimination and positive action were seen as integral aspects of their 'key duties':

- *Working towards the elimination of discrimination*
- *Promoting equality and affirmative action*
- *Promoting good relations between persons of different racial groups*
- *Overseeing the effectiveness of the statutory duty on public authorities*
- *Keeping under review the relevant legislation*

The passing of the RRO and Section 75 are still seen as historic milestones for race legislation, on which hopes for progressing race relations were pinned in the country (Chan-Hu,2023). However, when in the other devolved nations of the UK the Race Relations (Amendment) Act (2000) superseded the British Race Relations Act, Northern Ireland did not adjust the 1997 order. Effectively, this was translated as a continuation of the primary concern of in/equality being the management of ethno-political discrimination between those of 'Catholic/ nationalist') or 'Protestant/ Loyalist' 'community backgrounds'.

The body formulated to implement the Acts has continued to raise concerns that the

significant gaps between equality law in Great Britain (GB) and Northern Ireland (NI); gaps which have widened following the introduction of single equality legislation – the Equality Act 2010 – in Great Britain. These differences mean that in a number of key areas, individuals in Northern Ireland have less protection against discrimination and harassment than people in other parts of the United Kingdom. (ECNI, n.d.)

Various migrations to NI have continued in this time frame. In 2004 those from Eastern Europe, seeking better working conditions when their countries joined the European Union (of which NI was a part at the time), arrived and settled in both small towns and rural localities, in numbers larger than other areas of the UK (McAreevey, 2012). Over the next two decades, the Polish became what is the largest current non-NI-born group. From 2015, there was an increase in individuals and groups, who were seeking sanctuary in the UK, being resettled in NI. Since the mid-2010s, the rights, protections and sense of belonging for those who had settled in NI as part of the European Union have been up for negotiation since the Brexit process began.

Orientations to sociodemographic change

From race relations in the 1960's to ideas of community 'good relations' and 'inclusion', the language of integration in the UK has undergone numerous iterations in policy and practice (Murphy & Vieten, 2022). However, already within the first decade after the Good Friday Agreement, scholars raised concerns that the approach of Northern Ireland deradicalized both anti-sectarianism and anti-racism. It was argued to have adopted a "state formation that hides its incapacity to address rising racism and sectarianism under the fig leaf of 'good relations'" (McVeigh & Rolston, 2007, p. 1). McVeigh and Rolston (2007) articulated the factors that established conditions for racism to grow and thrive unadulterated in the early post-conflict period. They included what would have made post-conflict NI attractive to those beyond its borders, including peace in general, economic growth and shortages in labour. They also described how those migrants came to be targets for loyalist rage. This had to do primarily with their contact with loyalists when finding cheaper available accommodation (from de-industrialisation) in the segregated areas. Such accommodation was 'available, despite overcrowding in the nationalist working-class areas, because of the intimidation they would have faced. Loyalists of the time were described as suffering from alienation, because they lacked the gains of loyalist party politics and positive cultural affinities at the time. Of concern is the conclusion of this dilemma, where the state and public bodies made decisions about what to ignore, with "a reluctance to address anything that might further alienate loyalists - even their involvement in the racist violence" (McVeigh & Rolston, 2007, p. 12). It is because of such blinkeredness, that it is argued that sectarianism and racism should be looked at as intersecting in NI. That intersection created conditions where "being sectarian is an advantage in being racist" (McVeigh & Rolston, 2007, p. 13). Critiques have also been raised about the limited nature of approaching race-based

discrimination as demented individual acts of overt violence, rather than manifestations of the sectarian (McVeigh & Rolston, 2007), capitalist (Gilligan, 2019) or colonial system.

A factor impacting the under-serving and over-looking of migrants and minority ethnic populations may have to do with inadequate funding. This concern correlates with setbacks and delays in implementing equality strategies (Murphy & Vieten, 2017). When funds have been ringfenced (such as the Minority Ethnic Fund administered by The Executive Office (prior to that, The Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister), they have played a critical role in alleviating short-term hardships for minority ethnic communities, refugees, and asylum seekers. Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) such as charities and civil society organisations (CSOs) have played a significant role in bridging gaps between the needs of those seeking asylum and those granted refugee status, and the limited provision of services by the state and public bodies. Critical issues still needing to be addressed include anti-racism resources, integration projects, and barriers to accessing funding (Murphy & Vieten, 2022). This is despite Northern Ireland having been a beneficiary of the UK government's Vulnerable Persons Relocation Scheme (VPRS) (launched in 2014). It was established for the resettlement of Syrian refugees and asylum seekers, with those later arriving from Somalia and Syria, and more recently Afghanistan and the Ukraine. NI still did not have such a strategy at the time of writing, despite the Race Equality Strategy's recommendation of a separate Refugee Integration Strategy informed by a report produced by academics from a NI university (Murphy & Vieten, 2017), and the ten day window period was provided in 2022 for public consultation on a draft strategy (The Executive Office, 2022). All other regions of the UK have adopted a distinct refugee integration strategy.

Social regulation, determined and controlled by law, is in place to capacitate public authorities mandated and authorised to implement certain legislation on behalf of the NI state to address inequalities. Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act (1998) placed such 'statutory obligation' on two areas of duties for 'statutory authorities': 'Equality of Opportunity' and 'Good Relations'. Two Racial Equality Strategies have since been published by the Executive Office (2005-2010; 2015-2025) with slow, ineffectual rates of implementation and monitoring. The first of these framed its purpose as establishing:

a framework to tackle racial inequalities in Northern Ireland and to open up opportunity for all. To eradicate racism and hate crime and together with A Shared Future, to initiate actions to promote good race relations. (The Executive Office, 2005)

The second explicitly addressed the duties of public authorities and governance in its framing, and brought in a slight shift in discourse towards 'social cohesion:

The Racial Equality Strategy 2015 - 2025 establishes a framework for government departments (and others) to tackle racial inequalities, to eradicate racism and hate crime and along with Together: Building a

*United Community, to promote good race relations and social cohesion.
(The Executive Office, 2015)*

The various periods where the Northern Ireland Assembly ('Stormont') has stalled, is one of the reasons provided for the lack of progress on these strategies, and those to do with refugee integration, race relations, and the general programme for government. The Equality Commission and contributors to the report on The experiences of minority ethnic and migrant people in Northern Ireland published by the MPs on the House of Commons Northern Ireland Affairs Committee (2022) made apparent that, as late as 2021, that many of the recommendations from even the initial 2005-2010 strategy were still not yet in practice. Advocacy for recognition and for change continues actively to the present day.

Various groups, bodies and individuals have continued to raise concerns about the state of legislation and of inaction in the face of continued discrimination and hate crime. An independent review, with public consultation, of hate crime legislation in Northern Ireland, took place in 2020. To date, the legislation has not been passed. As with other groups, the MMETT (the partner organisation to this study) called upon the NI Department of Justice to introduce Hate Crime Legislation and a statutory definition of Hate Crime to ensure equal protection for all (Migrant and Minority Ethnic Thinktank, 2020). The Thinktank played a role in catalysing the responses of NI-based academic researchers to a UK-wide consultation on racial disparities and inequalities that year (Belluigi et al., 2020). Despite contributing evidence and recommendations informed by academic studies, it was ignored by that Commission, which then problematically went on to claim there was no institutional racism in the United Kingdom (Migrant and Minority Ethnic Thinktank, 2021). Dynamics and problematics such as these, provided the grounds on which this study arose.

This study found that such deferral, over-looking and avoidance characterises much the same dynamics when it has come to local majority groups' lack of interest in, prioritisation of and action to engage in academic research about these groups. It is a pattern of unresponsiveness that continues to the present day. The focus of the study is thus on the research production, agency and experiences of those whose practice has differed to this pattern, in the hopes of better supporting and extending such scholarship.

METHODOLOGICAL NOTES

Concerns about 'academic responsiveness' have been researched in a range of ways, with data from various sources and foci. This has included analysis of institutional cases, regional or national sectors, curricula, third mission activities, local investment and benefits of public-public and private-public partnerships by institutions, and the access and participation of staff and students.

The focus of this study on *academic research production* was informed by a scoping study which mapped prior academic output, for the purposes of providing non-academic readers access to academic knowledge about the experiences, knowledges and dynamics faced by migrants and minorities in NI (Lubit & Belluigi, 2021). That study was led by Dr Belluigi, with the assistance of Dr Lubit, in partnership with the Migrant and Minority Ethnic Thinktank (MMETT). The subject areas were determined by MMETT, which articulated the foci of particular concern to people grouped in NI as 'migrant' and 'ethnic minorities'. As indicated in Appendix B, these included criminal justice, education, employment, environment, health, housing, discrimination and legislation. Already articulated by the council members of the MMETT and others, was a sense that the universities were under-serving local persons of socio demographic groups 'ethnic minorities' and 'migrants'. Non-academic research, surveys and the voice of those of such groups were believed to have been responded to mostly by their civil society organisations, NGOs and by researchers outside of the context. It was also articulated that, for those in positions of policy making, implementations and governance, that academic research was given more legitimacy and thus may be more effective for change.

To gain rich data on such academic research production in this area of enquiry, publications were collated and analysed through a systematic literature review. Authors of these outputs were contacted for semi-structured in-depth interviews. Further insights were gained when engaging members of non-governmental organisations who partnered as part of such research, and research development offices from the context, to participate in report-and-respond discussions. This section outlines the approach and process undertaken in terms of these sources and methods, limitations and ethical considerations. As a report it is descriptive primarily for an audience not inducted into research on higher education or 'academic science'.

1. RESEARCH OUTPUT

The search and sift process

A systematic review of research outputs was conducted. A search was conducted via the databases of the two universities in Northern Ireland which are research intensive, with additional snowball sampling. The two universities are Queen's University Belfast and Ulster University. The universities utilise the Research Information Management System (RIMS) 'Pure' for the purpose of gathering what is called 'research intelligence' (i.e. the gathering of data on the outputs) and also for integration with external open access platforms. Direct access to information about Queen's University Belfast's outputs was via <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/>, and for Ulster University's outputs was via <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/>.

Information about the research engagement items were initially collated, categorised and archived during a prior study completed by March 2021, led by Dr Belluigi with the research assistance of Dr Lubit (see Lubit and Belluigi, 2021). The search method was duplicated in this study to include the period from March 2021-August 2022. A number of research items which were discovered through snowball sampling were also added. For instance, searching by author unearthed a number of outputs not uploaded to the database which met the criteria. Inclusion criteria were:

- Research subject: to do with 'migrants' or 'ethnic minorities'
- Geographic context: 'Northern Ireland'
- Authored by: academic citizens (students and staff) or Northern Irish universities

To fulfil our commitments to the partner organisation, new items found were added to the MME Research archive.

The process of identification, screening and inclusion in the final data set is visualisation below.

Figure 1
Flow chart of identification, screening and inclusion of research outputs

Reference data about each publication was saved to the online reference management software. All publicly accessible research items themselves were downloaded; those available through Queen's University Belfast library licencing were added to that folder, as were those attained through inter-library assistance or by contacting the authors directly. However, 9 of the items were not fully accessible³.

Type	Author	P/ACI	Institutional Base	Sex/Other demographic	Date	Discipline	Subject Matter	Methodological	Orientation	Sources	Positioning of MME people	Details: Social Groups	Intersection	Methods	Ethical	
Blog Post	as above			as above	as above	2021	as above	as above		Yes	2. Participant & Author	Somalia/Sudan/Sri Lanka	Genderism	as above	No	
Report	Andy Biggart Liam O'Hare Paul Connolly	PI	QUB QUB	Male Male Male	2008	Health	EBAME Children	Mixed Method	Epidemiological App	Yes	2. Participant	BAVE/Asian Travellers/Eastern Europe	Epidemiological Survey/FO	YES	Ethical	
Journal Article	as above			as above	2010	Education	Belorepof/Enclave	Mixed Method	as above	Yes	2. Participant	Irish Traveller/Chinese/Asian & Ex	as above	YES	as above	
Book Section	Mairéad Mc Craik Amanda Mc Mullan	PI	Ulster	Female	2006	Human Geog	Chinese, Indian and	Quantitative		No	1. Subject of the Study	Ethno-microethn/Religion	Spatial Analysis of Census	NO		
Report	Luis Michael Pádra Deane	PI	HRREC QUB	Female	2018	Social Science	understanding sent	Secondary Data		No	1. Subject of the Study	asylum seekers/refugees/Syrian	Comparative Analyses of M	NO		
Book	Irvin Egan Duncan Morov Dorrick Wilson	PI	NI Ulster	Female Male	1997	Social Science	Community relation	Conceptual		No	1. Subject of the study	Minority ethnic groups	Analysis of community-rela	No		
Book Section	Paul Hanzworth Chris Gilligan Aidan McDermott	PI	Ulster University Ulster	Male Male Male	2009	Social Science	Attitudes of Eleve	Empirical		NO	1. Subject of the Study	Minority ethnic communitie	Survey/semi-structured int	NO		
Journal Article	as above			as above	2008	as above	as above	as above		NO	1. Subject of the Study	as above	Survey	NO		
Journal Article	Philip McDermott	PI	Ulster	Male	2006	Education	Educational planning	Mixed Methods		YES	2. Participants	India/Chinese/Eastern Europe	Archival research/Interview	NO		
Report	Jennifer Hamilton Fiona Bloomer John Bell Jane Healy	PI	Ulster	Female Male Male Female	2007	Education	Educational provision	Mixed Methods		Yes	2. Participants	Northern Irish Traveller/Parents/Ch	Focus groups/Discussion	NO		
Journal Article	Jennifer Hamilton Fiona Bloomer Michael Potter	PI	as above Ulster	Female Male	2012	Education	as above	Mixed Method	as above	Yes	2. Participants	as above	as above	Focus groups/semi struc	NO	
Journal Article	Fiona Bloomer Potter & Hamilton	PI	Ulster	Female	2013	as above	as above	Mixed Method	as above	Yes	2. Participants	as above	as above	YES	Ethical	
Book Section	as above			as above	2016	as above	Traveller Education	Mixed Methods		Yes	2. Participants	as above	as above	as above	NO	
Report	Luis Michael	PI	HRREC	Female	2015	Social Science	Microphobia/Racism	Qualitative & Quantitative		Yes	1. Subject of the Study	Black African/Black	Sexuality/O	Data collected from online	NO	
Journal Article	Joanna Nicholas Patricia Drouine John Sheldon Sarah Best	PI	Ulster	Female	2016	Social Work	Evaluational/MGALA	Mixed Methods		No	1. Subject of the Study	Black minority ethnic/	Children & Y	File Audit/Questionnaire	NO	
Policy Brief	Fiona Murphy Ulrike Vieten	PI	QUB QUB	Female Female	2017	Social Science	Development of FR	Mixed Method	Quantitative & Qualitative	Yes	2. Participants, Co-Author	Asylum Seekers & Refugees		Questionnaire/Semi-struct	NO	
Report	as above			as above	2017	as above	Refugee Integration	Mixed Method	as above	Yes	2. Participants, Co-Author	Asylum Seekers & Refugees - Somalia,	N/A	as above	YES	Project
Blog Post	as above			as above	2017	as above	Astar's personal st	Qualitative		Yes	2. Participants, Co-Author	as above & Somalia	Interview	NO		

Figure 2 Spreadsheet with information extracted from publications included in the systematic review

The systematic review process

Once the data set was collected, a systematic review was carried out on all items. Firstly, the items were synthesized into 'projects' (where appropriate), of which there were 159. Projects included the various methods of the research outputs (such as reports, journal articles, books, blog articles et cetera) that related to the same research project.

Secondly, as visualised below information was extracted from the outputs and recorded on a spreadsheet in either direct quotes, key words or numerical indicators.

The columns in the spreadsheet relate to categories tabulated below. This provided a framework for mapping the content of the outputs, which enabled the researchers to ask questions across the dataset.

³ Links to these 9 research items in the PURE databases were broken. Where possible, authors were contacted, however those contacted were unable to locate the items. The Pure data provided a brief description or abstract, the author's name and outlined the year of publication, the type of output, the subject matter and the discipline. However, it was not possible to read through the actual text, and from it glean specific details.

Category	Sub-category	
A	Type of output	(report, journal article, book section etc.)
B	Author info	i. Name(s)
		ii. Primary Investigator/Co-Investigator
		iii. Institutional affiliations (within NI and/or outside (by country))
		iv. Available demographic information of the authors
C	About the projects	
		i. Date
		ii. Discipline(s)
		iii. Subject matter
		iv. Methodology
		Orientation/ paradigm
		Sources
		Details about inclusion of participants and in what capacity/ positioning
		Details about which social groups and any intersections
		Methods
		v. Information about ethics compliance, conduct and concerns
		vi. Recommendations for research (what stated)
		viii. Recommendations for policy/ practices (what stated)
		viii. Funding
		Yes/ No
		What funder; internal institutional funds; unfunded
		Information about location of funder
		x. Information about the partners of the research
		xi. Reflections/ reflexive statements by the authors

Table 1 Content extracted from research output items.

The specific information that was quantified was then visualised in a report (Moynihan and Belluigi, 2023), figures from which have been included herein. That report was utilised in report-and-respond discussions with the member of non-academic organisations that were named as partners of the projects in the outputs, and with research development officers, as discussed below. A summary of the analysis from this data appears in the Summary of Findings Part A.

2. THE AUTHORS OF RESEARCH OUTPUT

The participants

Primary data was generated with three groups of participants: authors, non-academic organisations, and research development officers.

The authors were selected from the list of 247 authors of the 209 research items described above. Thus, all the researchers/ academics who were participants of this study, had authored academic research output, where at least one of the authors

were based at a Northern Irish research-intensive institution. It should be noted that research has been undertaken in this area of enquiry in Northern Ireland by independent researchers, non-academic bodies and journalists, for instance. The study by no means is intended to denigrate or unrecognize such contributions. Further research mapping and examining such research is warranted. In addition, there has been academic research produced about this area of enquiry and populations in Northern Ireland by academics based in universities outside of Northern Ireland. A comparative study would be of interest to comprehend the difference in conditions for such academic agents. However, the questions that this study sought to address were about the research landscape and climate that pertained to academic knowledge production in Northern Ireland about that which is 'local' to it.

Authors were contacted via email, and invited to participate in an interview or to respond to an online questionnaire. Of those invited, 32 elected to participate. Of these, 7 completed and submitted the questionnaire; 25 agreed to take part in a full interview. The questions posed in both methods were the same.

Figure 3 The time period when participating authors were research-active in this area of enquiry

Participants were asked to indicate the timeframe when they engaged in this area of enquiry. The number of participants reflecting on research conducted 20-30 years ago was 1 (1992-2002); 10 - 20 years ago were 7 (2002-2012); 10 had conducted research in the period 6 - 10 years ago (2012-2017); and over 15 had conducted research in the past 0-5 years (2017-2022). Thus all periods were reflected upon. Six had experience gained during the 10 years; and one for 20 years. Thus, a range of experiences informed the study. Participants included staff of permanent contracts at various levels of the academic hierarchy; researchers on short term contracts; and those who had completed their doctoral studies or had published as students. Thus, insights from a range of academic citizens who were research-active in this area informed this study.

These participants were asked to self-identify aspects of their social location in relation to the study subject; and also, to indicate how they were categorized by the UK government. This was in recognition that the two may not be in alignment.

Figure 4 Visualization comparing how participating authors reported they were categorised in the UK (top) with how they self-identified (bottom)

The majority of participating authors neither identified nor were categorized in Northern Ireland as migrants or ethnic minorities.

Figure 4 visualises the contrast between how the authors self-identified and how they believed they were categorized according to the legislation of the UK government. Almost a third (31%) identified as migrants, whether internal to the island of Ireland, the United Kingdom or Europe, or as external migrants. The largest contrast is in those who identified as ethnic minorities in various ways, which added to 50% of the participating academics; yet they recognized that most of them were not seen as ethnic minorities according to the racialization of ethnicity in Northern Ireland, where only 9% were categorized in that way. The question itself created discussion during the interviews, with participants expressing disagreement with the collapse of race into ethnicity and the impoverished categories for identities offered within the UK.

The participating authors were asked to respond to open-ended questions and closed statements. The schedule of questions is reproduced in Appendix D. The questions elicited insights about three broad aspects: the authors themselves and their relation to the area of enquiry; conditions related to the area of enquiry in Northern Ireland; and a range of varied questions about perceptions and discourses of such research. The questionnaire consisted of 22 questions. 10 of these questions were open-ended where a text box was provided to allow participants to submit a qualitative answer. The other 12 questions were of Likert scale design, where each question offered between 4 to 7 responses, of which the participant was allowed to select only

one. Three of these Likert style questions were about the researcher's positioning, for example, did they identify as a migrant and/or as a minority ethnic person and then how were they identified in this regulatory environment. The other 7 questions were related to the research life cycle which is outlined in more detail in the next section. The Likert scale questions were also asked of the interview participants; however, they were given the option to expand their answers to the questions if they wished to do so. Finally, all of the results were collated into one document for content analysis.

As mentioned above, the authors were asked seven questions about the research life cycle in the questionnaire. The questions posed were specifically around research in the area of migrant/minority ethnic groups in NI. The initial question was had they conducted such research? There were only 4 possible answers to this and to all of the other questions in the research life cycle section and they were a) No b) for 1 project only c) for 2 projects or more or d) no answer. Then the participants were asked if they had conducted such research and published from it. The next 3 questions were concerned with funding, and they were: have you applied for funding for such research; have you been awarded funding for such research; and finally, have you contributed to unfunded or self-funded research in this area? Then the participant was asked if they had wanted to conduct research in this area, but for various reasons had not done so yet; and finally, they were asked if they had contributed to proposals about such research which have not progressed to projects. As above, the research life cycle questions were also asked to those who took part in interviews, but they were encouraged to expand on their answers if they wished to do so.

The interviews were transcribed and cleaned of identifiers, and opportunity provided for each participant to member-check the transcription and make amendments or additions. The responses to the questionnaires were also cleaned. Both of these were then added to the data set, and coded.

Initial codebooks were developed by Dr Belluigi and Ms Moynihan independently, and then in conversation, developed into a single codebook. This process involved first converting what was said to text (transcribing the interviews) and the qualitative answers from the questionnaire were collated. The next step then was discovering some kind of pattern by attaching labels to these articulations. The structure of the interview schedule for the one-to-one interviews was used as a template, which began with the researchers' motivations to undertake the research to its impacts on them personally and professionally; and then to enablements and constraints they encountered while doing the research and so on. Similar codes were grouped together and assigned a category name and embedded under the appropriate area. An inductive method of coding was then used, where the codes 'emerged' from the data. Line by line coding was used to extract detailed and specific data so as to capture as much richness from the data set as possible. This allowed for analysis to be undertaken systematically. The summary outlined in Part B of the Findings section is informed by this analysis.

The report-and-respond discussions

Of the 14 non-academic organisations named or attributed involvement in the outputs analysed (what we have termed 'partners' in this study, as per current UK research terminology), 2 organisations responded. Of those, only 1 had capacity to participate – the African and Caribbean Support Organisation of Northern Ireland (ACSONI). Three members of that NGO participated in a three hour long report-and-respond discussion about the interim report (Moynihan & Belluigi, 2022). The engagement had much value for confirming and deepening the interpretations and providing the perspective of an organization that had been involved in such research for a considerable number of years. However, it is a limitation of this study that there was not more involvement of such partners.

Opportunities were provided for those working within the research offices of both institutions to participate in the study. The interim report was shared with all those emailed requesting participation. Responses indicated that most had not yet experienced research about research ('academic science'/ research on higher education) in this context or their careers. There also seemed reluctance to be involved for fear of professional repercussions. Of those invited, 2 research officers participated. Their insights were very helpful in understanding the larger funding policy environment. Indications were that the interim findings were mutually beneficial.

3. ETHICAL CLEARANCE, CONDUCT AND REFLECTIONS

Ethical clearance for this study was granted by the Ethical Research Committee of Queen's University Belfast School of Social Sciences, Education and Social Work (REF 067_2021). The study process practiced ethical conduct in terms of the rights of participants and their informed, active consent; in addition to complying with protections of private data as per General Data Protections Regulations (GDPR). Invited participants were provided an information sheet about the study, outlining their rights and guidance for engagement. Opportunities were provided for asking questions prior to providing consent and permission. Opportunities were also provided for member-checking of transcripts prior to inclusion in the dataset. Anonymity for participants was the default; however, the partner organisation and NGO which participated preferred for their participation to be recognised and named.

A choice was made to name the two institutions from which the outputs were collected, but not to indicate the institutional base within which the participating authors were situated. This was to protect the participants from identification or unintended professional risk. Because this study is not an evaluation nor a case study, it is not appropriate to suggest that the dynamics are specific to a particular institution. Rather the findings refer to the climate, culture or landscape – indicating a spatial relation. Where possible, a temporal relation was also made, where there were indications in the shifts of such cultures over time.

The principles of transparency and inclusion were applied from planning through to the selection of participants and analysis. These included:

- The initial impetus was borne from conversations with council members of the Migrant and Minority Ethnic ThinkTank when pondering the politics of representation and participation in Northern Ireland; and the initial scoping review was undertaken in partnership with that organisation. Specific questions posed to authors came directly from roundtable discussions with the council members, following the publication of that report.
- Outputs were inclusive of all the items that matched the search criteria that had been uploaded by their authors on the institutions' repositories.
- Opportunities were created for all relevant authors to participate, by inviting all those cited in the research outputs. These were invited by direct email, a process repeated three times over a five-month period. Their responses were generated independently and anonymously online; or via an audio-recorded meetings held in person or online at a time and date convenient to them. Participants were invited to comment on or problematise the questions posed, and terms used within the study.
- All named non-academic partners in the outputs studied, were invited to participate. These were invited by direct email, a process repeated three times over a two-month period. Their responses were generated via an audio-recorded meeting in person meeting in their offices, at a time and date convenient to them. Participants were invited to comment on or problematise the interpretations shared, and terms used within the study. The option was provided for their participation to be acknowledged by name or anonymously – this was discussed at the beginning of the process, and once this report was complete. The feedback of that organisation was also elicited on this report.
- Members of the universities' research officers, and their managers, were invited by direct email, a process repeated three times over a two-month period. Their responses were generated via an audio-recorded meetings held online at a time and date convenient to them. Participants were invited to comment on or problematise the interpretations shared, and terms used within the study. This was in an attempt to balance, or at least complicate, the perspectives of the authors with more institutional perspectives of those driving research development.

A central consideration of this study was the politics of authorship and representation, and as such there is a tension in that it is authored by those who are not local to the context. The study was led by Dr Dina Zoe Belluigi with input of two research assistants. Ms Yvonne Moynihan carried out the systematic literature review and assisted with the content analysis of the qualitative interviews and questionnaires. Input into design elements and the context section was contributed by Ms Stella Attah. All three of us

are what could be described as migrant academic citizens within Northern Ireland. That is, we all had our formative years of childhood outside of the intimate knowledges of those settled in the country, and outside of the majority norms of the bubble of the university. However, both Yvonne and Stella formed much of their academic citizenry as postgraduates within Northern Ireland.

As primary investigator, Dr Belluigi took the leading role in designing the project. She had been living with her South African family in Northern Ireland as an academic for 5 years before commencing the study. She is racialised as 'white' within the host country and that of her birth, thus bringing insider experiences of contexts of racialisation which advantage white citizens, albeit that NI is a majority 'white' setting. As a double migrant of (predominantly) Greek South African background, she has intergenerational memory of the complexities of minority populations who negotiate their marginal social positioning within conditions of coloniality, partition and division. The study was very much intended as both a process of learning from colleagues who negotiate and persevere within the academic conditions in which she was placed; and to contribute academic knowledge about the research ecology in an understudied academic context. She was conscientised partly through her experience as a mother and person living and working in NI where re-racialisation was similar to her experiences of apartheid South Africa, and disabled identification and solidarity with fellow Africans. She was informed more thoroughly of the struggles for equality led by ethnic minorities in NI, through the discussions, insights and knowledge of the fellow Council members of the Migrant and Minority Ethnic Thinktank from 2020.

Originally from the Republic of Ireland, Yvonne moved to Northern Ireland in 2017 to study a masters with Queen's University, Belfast where she was reading for a PhD at the time of writing. Therefore, she had also been living in Northern Ireland for 5 years before beginning work on this study. Yvonne identifies as an economic migrant within Northern Ireland. She is also racialized in both countries as 'white' and brings insider experience of a context that, similarly to NI, is homogenous, in terms of 'white' ethnicity/race, English speaking and of 'Christian' background and religious belief. Yvonne two postgraduate studies have focused on generating knowledge about, and with, children who are migrants within NI and their educational experiences.

In 2021, Stella, hailing from Nigeria, moved to Northern Ireland to study for a master's at Queen's University. Stella identifies as an African economic migrant and had lived in Northern Ireland for 2 years before joining the project. Her understanding of Northern Ireland and its major societal challenges was grounded in her postgraduate studies, which focused on conflict transformation and social justice. Through her research for this project and insights from the interim report, Stella gained valuable knowledge about the experiences and ethnic minorities and migrants in Northern Ireland, contributing to her awareness of the subject matter.

As academic citizens, we are insiders to the academic communities and universities we were researching. We adopted safeguards against possible professional intrusion

of employers and colleagues and respected the confidentiality of our sources. To mitigate against blind spots in our interpretation and insights into the societal complexities of the context, particularly those which may have happened over 30 years ago, we engaged with local persons by sharing drafts and holding discussions during the project.

To expand our vision beyond the particular, the project was discussed with members of an external advisory group. These were composed of those with academic expertise and experiential knowledge, based both in Northern Ireland and from across the world. They are (in alphabetical order) Dr Najma Aghardien (University of Witwatersrand); Dr Dickson Ajisafe (International scholar); Dr Mohammad-Albarra Hassan (Essex University Online); Professor Jason Arday (Cambridge University); Dr Cath Camps (University of South Wales); Dr Colletta Dalikeni (Dundalk Institute of Technology); Dr Nandita Banerjee Dhawan (Jadavpur University); Professor Andre Keet (Nelson Mandela University); Professor Chris Knaus (University of Washington); Ms Akhona Maqungo (Rhodes University); Dr Toma Pustelnikovaite (Cardiff University); Dr Giff Sotonye-Frank (Queen's University Belfast); and Ms Joy-Tendai Kangere (Law Library, Ireland; Rooted in Africa and Ireland).

Local external advice and discussion were also provided by the council members of the Migrant and Minority Ethnic Thinktank. Dr Belluigi was a council member at the time of writing. The project was conceived from a prior project led by her, in partnership with the MMETT and funded by Queen's University Belfast's ESRC Impact Acceleration Account (Lubit & Belluigi, 2021). The MMETT was updated throughout the research process, and invited to provide input, feedback and direction. Members of the MMETT served as external advisors during the appointment process of the research assistants; and in providing direct insights about the counter-histories of NI, some of which informed the 'context' section of the report. Drafts of this report were shared with the MMETT, whose council approved the acknowledgement of their role as partners, subject to addressing a number of concerns. These included where readership may misinterpret references to colonialism; the nomenclature related to ethnic minorities who are racialised as other-than white in NI; and clarifying aspects of policy regulation in the 'context' section. Following that, acknowledgment of the partnership relationship was unanimously approved.

This report has been developed to provide non-academic publics open access to the research process and findings. This approach was agreed upon by the authors and the MMETT, for the purposes of contributing to this area of enquiry. This was not a requirement of the funding body.

A note on authorial voice and tone in this document. As the reader will note in the discussions section, one of the findings of this study was how academic authors negotiated the complexities of the research environment and the social environment, in the various representations of academic knowledge. Similarly, we deliberated what content, words, tone and the extent of critique to be expressed in this report.

A decision was made to describe the summaries of the analysis, and point towards the general findings, with a brief discussion. This seemed most appropriate for attempting to widen its impact, by allowing for various readers to make interpretations from the descriptions. The readership intended were practitioners (in this case, both authors and research developers), non-academic groups or organisations, and general NI publics. Further depth and expression of the application of academic analysis will be represented in academic dissemination that is peer reviewed. These will be added to the project website following peer reviewed publication (see <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/projects/academic-research-responsiveness-to-ethnic-minorities-and-migrants>).

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This section provides a summary of the findings. It should be noted that at this point this is aimed at an audience not steeped in higher education studies, and thus has not been theorised with those lenses nor articulated in the jargon of that field. Such analysis and discussion will be presented in academic outputs in time.

The section is divided into Part A with the findings of the systematic literature review; followed by a summary of the content analysis of data generated from academic authors in Part B.

PART A: FINDINGS OF THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

The findings are divided into four sections. A general overview of the outputs, projects, dates of production and nature of the outputs is presented in 1. This is then followed by insights into funding of this research because of the foundational role that external research funding now plays to enabling research in research-intensive universities in the context of underfunding of NI institutions (2). The review then turns to look at methodological aspects of studies (3), and the last section the positioning of research participants (4), including those of the studied populations and researchers themselves.

1. Grouping the output: Projects, output types and dates of publication

The amount of research items archived on the institutional repositories was 208, with a further 6 identified through snowball sampling from contacting the authors or reference lists. From these, 209 outputs in total met the criteria of the study. However, because 9 were not fully accessible, 200 were analysed in depth.

Figure 5 visualises research projects and their outputs, and the total of recorded items which were analysed for this study. A certain number of these 209 outputs stemmed

from projects and these were grouped accordingly during analysis into 159 projects. 62 of these projects explicitly mentioned funding (more on this from p.38). Of the 159 projects, 36 had recorded the production of only 1 output. 23 projects produced more than one output, which a combined production of 72 outputs in total. Of these, 15 projects had 2 outputs; 2 had 3 outputs; 2 had 4 outputs; 1 project had 5 outputs; there was 1 with 7; and 2 projects with 8 outputs. Types of outputs in relation to funded projects are outlined In Part A.2.

Figure 5 The relation of the amount of projects to the amount of outputs

Figure 6 Timeline indicating growth in research output

Outputs related to the area of enquiry were published from 1994 to July 2022. As can be seen in Figure 6 the number of outputs has fluctuated over the past 28 years. There has clearly been a marked increase in the volume of outputs in the past ten years. However, there was a notable drop in production from 2021 where only 3 outputs were recorded. It is possible research activity and/or publication was adversely impacted by the Covid19 period; reduced access to European funding streams after

Brexit; or other factors, such as a reduction in incentives for academics to upload texts after the 2021 deadline for the Research Excellence Framework (REF) which occurs every 8 years. When analysing this timeline, consideration has been given to social changes that may have had impact, such as increases in migration or public discourse or interest in certain groups or topics. In addition, academic factors of consideration are at play too, such as funding awarded (which is outlined below), what information can be gathered about changes to disciplines, centres or institutes which had interest in these areas; and to university's third mission. A suggestion for future research would be to consider which projects (if any) were selected as 'Impact Case Studies' for the UK-wide research assessment exercise (the Research Excellence Framework (REF)), considering that is a way of promoting research at universities.

Figure 7 Output types categorised by their purpose of academic dissemination and non-academic engagement or impact

A range of output types was found. In the visual above the output types have been separated into 2 categories. The first is 'dissemination' which included journal articles (72), book sections (25), doctoral theses⁴ (14), conference and concept papers (11), books (6) and presentations (2). The second category is 'impact' which included reports (55), blogs (9), media outputs (6), policy documents (6) [which included 3 policy briefs, 2 written evidence and 1 oral evidence], art projects (2) [which included 2 art exhibitions and 1 short film] and forum posts (1).

In general, within academia, that which contributes to academic knowledge (and thus has most legitimacy, and also greater potential for sustainability within

⁴ Northern Ireland's universities have only recently become compliant with open access requirements for dissertations at doctoral level. As such, it is possible that additional studies have been undertaken which have not been uploaded by students/ supervisors to the public-facing repositories.

academia) is published as dissemination of research most often in the form of books, book sections or journal articles. As indicated in Figure 7, there were 103 academic outputs, which was 49% of the total output. The remaining 51% were either reports (55 of 209 items), or for 'pathways to impact'. These are generally 'translation' documents, aimed at non-academic readers in the hopes they then translate the findings into change in policy and practice. Thus, the prevalence of translation/impact-related output for this area of enquiry is possibly indicative of the function of such research, i.e. as an evidence-base for advocacy or evaluation.

2. Analysis of the funding of this area of enquiry

The funding of research is an area of interest for this study. Questions asked of the dataset about funding included such considerations as: *do funding patterns change over time? how is funding an enabler of such research?; what types of research do specific funders engender?; from whence does the funding come?; and how much is undertaken unfunded?.* As such, data about funding was extracted from what was written and acknowledged within the outputs. Findings are displayed in visualisations in this section. Refer to Part B for participating authors' insights about funding.

Figure 8 Number of projects funded over time

Overall, 62 of the 158 projects explicitly wrote about funding. Figure 8 shows the number of projects funded over time. While the first project was funded in 1997, funding over the next 10 years remained low (a total of 6 projects). However, 2008 saw a significant shift with the number of projects awarded funding rising to 5. The following decade saw a fairly steady stream of funding with an average of 3 projects a year being financially supported. The year 2018 saw a dramatic increase to 11 projects funded. In 2019 the numbers began to drop again and, at the time of writing, there have been no new projects funded since 2020. It should be noted that information related to the date of funding award was not available to us; thus, it is possible that awards were made a considerable time prior to the publication date mapped here.

The 62 projects that were funded (of the 158 total projects) had resulted in a total of 99 outputs which accounted for almost half of all outputs reviewed (49%). Twelve of these outputs were partly and/or jointly funded by different funders and across funding streams (i.e. governmental, non-governmental/non-academic and academic).

The funding streams can be seen in Figure 9. The greatest number of projects were funded by non-governmental/non-academic sources, which were 18 projects (with 34 related outputs). Academic sources funded 17 projects (with 19 outputs). While the Northern Ireland government funded only 16 projects, they resulted in 31 outputs. European/ overseas (non-UK) organisations provided funding for 10 projects (with 13 outputs). The UK government (through UKAID) funded 1 project (with 2 outputs).

Figure 9 Comparison of funding streams with project and output amounts

It is important to note that outputs were also partly and/or jointly funded. The one UK government funded project was full funding; the NI government bodies funded all but 3 of their outputs solely. Academic bodies jointly funded 3 outputs and non-governmental/non-academic bodies funded 4 of outputs with other funders. In total, the number of outputs that were jointly or partly funded was 12.

Figure 11, the various output types of the individual funding streams are displayed. The column for total outputs has been placed at the back, in order to view the output types clearly. It shows that most Northern Ireland government funding was spent on reports (10 out of 31 outputs). Their next most funded output type were journal articles (7, of which 2 were partly or jointly funded) and then 4 book sections. The majority of non-academic funding was also spent on reports (13; of which 3 were partly or jointly funded); such sources also funded 10 journal articles (of which 1 was partly or jointly funded). Academic funders supported 12 journal articles (3 of which were jointly or partly funded) and a total of 5 reports and 2 doctoral theses. The majority of European and other overseas funding was used for reports (6; of which 1 was partly or jointly funded); however, the number of journal articles funded was 5, and a total of 2 book

sections (both of which were partly or jointly funded). The project the UK government funded resulted in 2 outputs: 1 report and 1 journal article.

Figure 10 Non-governmental/ non-academic funding bodies by project and output

The majority of projects were funded by non-governmental/non-academic organisations as seen in Figure 10. The Joseph Rowntree Foundation (JRF) provided funding for 6 projects which resulted in 10 outputs. The Nuffield Foundation funded 3 projects which generated 9 outputs (however, 2 of these were only partly funded). The Rotary International and Capital Rotary Club supplied funding for 2 projects (with 2 outputs). The Northern Ireland Commissioner for Children and Young People (NICCY) funded 1 project which generated 4 outputs overall. Belfast Exposed (with the Project Arts Centre, Republic of Ireland) funded 1 project which resulted in 3 outputs. ROSA Northern Ireland (ROSA NI) funded 1 project (with 2 outputs). The Northern Ireland Council for Ethnic Minorities (NICEM) funded 1 project with 1 output; as did the Garfield Weston and the Big Lottery Fund. The Legal Education Foundation and Football for Hope both supported projects which produced 1 output (however, they were partly funded).

Of the output types funded by non-governmental/ non-academic bodies, the greatest number were funded by the Nuffield Foundation (9) and the Joseph Rowntree Foundation (JRF) (10). One of the projects Nuffield funded (led by Professor McAreavey) and produced 8 outputs: 1 report (partly funded by Peace III); 4 journal articles (one of which was co-authored with Chaitali Das), 1 book section and 1 magazine article. The other 2 Nuffield outputs were journal articles which were partly funded (both were jointly funded with JRF; Queen's University Belfast partly funded one). JRF funded 10 outputs, 6 of these were reports, 2 policy documents, 1 journal article and 1 presentation. Four of the projects with just one output were reports, of which 2 were partly funded: 1 by Football for Hope and the other by Legal Education Foundation (which was also supported by JRF).

Figure 11 Funding streams with detail of output types

Figure 12 Academic funding bodies with project and output amount

Academic funding was provided for 17 of the projects which resulted in a total of 19 outputs overall (Figure 12). The majority of the funding came from the Economic Social and Research Council (ESRC) which provided funding for 7 projects resulting in 9 outputs (2 part funded, details below). The Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) funded 2 projects (with 2 outputs). The Higher Education Innovation Fund funded 2 projects (with 2 outputs). Internal funding by one of the universities supported 3 projects with 3 outputs. British Academy/ Leverhulme funded 1 project with 1 output. The United Kingdom for International Education (with Ulster University) funded 1 project with 1 output. Finally, the Standing Conference of Teacher Education North and South (SCoTENS) project produced one output which was jointly funded with Ulster University and the Marino Institute of Education (Republic of Ireland).

ESRC funding was mostly used for the production of journal articles (6 out of 9), however 2 of these were partly funded by the Academy of Finland and the Medical Research Council. One of the universities funded 3 outputs, 2 of those were doctoral theses and 1 journal article. The UK Council for International Education and Ulster University jointly funded a journal article. A SCoTENS report was jointly funded by Ulster University and the Marino Institute for Education.

Government funding accounted for 16 projects which resulted in 31 outputs in total (Figure 13). The majority of the projects were funded by the Department for the Economy⁵ who funded 6 projects with 6 outputs (including 2 partly funded projects). The Office of First Minister and Deputy First Minister/The Executive Office (OFMDFM/TEO) funded 3 projects (with 3 outputs); The Northern Ireland Racial Equality Unit funded 1 project (8 outputs); Northern Ireland Social Steering Group funded 1

⁵ The Department for the Economy (DfE) is a devolved Northern Ireland government department in the Northern Ireland Executive. Some of these projects were funded by departments whose functions have now transferred to the DfE, e.g. the Department of Employment and Learning; the Department of Education and Learning, and as such they have been included herein.

project (with 8 outputs); Northern Ireland Department of Justice (NIDOJ) funded 1 project (with 2 outputs). The remaining bodies - the Department of Health's Office of Social Services; the Department of Research and Development and the Education Authority's Inclusion and Diversity Service- each funded one project with one output. The Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency (NISRA) supported 1 project with 1 output through part funding. Overall, the UK Government (UKAID) funded 1 project which resulted in 2 outputs.

Figure 13 Government funding (inclusive of Northern Ireland and the UK) by project and outputs

The greatest number of outputs were funded by the Racial Equality Unit, Social Steering Groups and the Department for the Economy (DfE). The DfE provided funding for 3 doctoral theses and 3 journal articles of which 2 were partly funded, with funding from JRF and Nuffield. The Racial Equality unit funded one project by Dr Murphy and Dr Vieten which generated 8 outputs, among them 1 report, 2 journal articles, 3 blog posts, 1 book section and 1 policy document. Likewise, the Social Steering group's funding for a project led by Professor Connolly resulted in 8 outputs. These included 4 reports (3 of which were co-authored with Dr Keenan), 3 book sections (one with Dr Keenan and one with Dr Khaoury) and 1 journal article (also with Dr Keenan). The NISRA report authored by Dr Irwin and Dr Dunn was jointly funded with the European Community Physical and Social Environment Programme.

European and overseas bodies provided funding for 10 projects which resulted in 13 outputs in total (Figure 14). The EU (European Union) provided most of this funding through various different bodies. The EU Programme for Peace funded 3 projects resulting in 5 outputs (1 part funded). European Union Horizon2020 (EU H2020) funded 1 project (with 1 output); the European Peace III Programme (EU Peace III) funded 1 project (with 1 output); the European Network for Racism (ENAR) provided funding for 1 project with 1 output; Humanities in the European Research Area (HERA) partly funded 1 project with 1 output. The Republic of Ireland Health and Service Executive (ROI HSE) provided funding for 1 project with 1 output. Friedrich Ebert Stiftung

Academic Foundation funded 1 project with 1 output. Atlantic Philanthropies provided funding for 1 project which resulted in 2 outputs.

Figure 14 European and overseas funding by projects and outputs

As was mentioned above, the EU Programme for Peace funded the majority of outputs in this section (5 outputs, including 2 reports and 2 journal articles). One of these journal articles and a book section (partly funded) were part of a project by Drs Hainsworth, Gilligan and McGarry. Six of the projects in this section produced just one output (3 reports, 2 journal articles, 1 book section). The book section authored by Dr Svasek acknowledged funding from the AHRC, AKA, DASTI, ETF, HERA, FNR, FWF, HAZU, IRCHSS, MHEST, NOW, RANNIS, RCN, VR and The European Community FP7 2008-2013.

3. Analysis of the methodological aspects of the research output

In this section, aspects of the methodology of the projects are outlined, including the discipline, approach to method of data generation or collection, which social groups the studies considered, and how such social groups were positioned within the methodologies. These are represented per research output.

3.1. Disciplinary orientation

Research items did not always fit neatly into a particular discipline and/or may be interdisciplinary. In this case the most relevant overarching discipline was chosen. If, for instance the research item was related to psychology and anthropology (social sciences) but also had elements of law (humanities) then it was linked to the social science discipline. If, however, there was a dominant sub discipline, for example, hospitality and management then this was chosen.

The vast majority of studies were in the Social Sciences (58) which accounts for 27% of production. Education had 23 outputs (11% of the total), followed by Human Geography with 17 outputs (8%). After this the numbers for each discipline fall substantially. Anthropology, Human Rights and Social Policy had 13 outputs each. Health had 12. Applied Social and Political Sciences had 10, Law had 9 and Conflict Transformation had 8 outputs. Psychology, Sport, and Arts and Performance had 5 outputs each. Hospitality and Tourism and Social Work had 4 each. Humanities, Social Business and Management, Research Methods and Criminal Justice had 2 outputs each. Public Policy and Communications and Museum and Heritage studies had 1 output each.

3.2 Approach to data collection and generation

Figure 15 Approach to data collection and generation

Figure 15 visualises the methods of the 200 accessible research outputs. Most of the research items reviewed involved the generation of qualitative data. It was uniquely used in 85 outputs in total (that is over 40% of all outputs). Mixed method approaches (i.e. a combination of qualitative and quantitative) was used in 45 outputs. 21 outputs used a strictly quantitative approach. Approaches using secondary data were in 34 outputs and 15 research items were of conceptual or philosophical studies.

4. Analysis of the positioning and participation of research participants involved in the research process

4.1 Positioning of the social groups studied

Figure 16 Positioning, participation and authorship of social groups in the research reviewed by output

A concern of this project was the positioning of the social groups to which such enquiry relates (Figure 16). The largest proportion were as objects of study – 99 in total (48%). The number of outputs which included them participants was 94 (45%) in total. Very few outputs named partner organisations (7). A total of 31 outputs were co-authored by an MME person or persons (almost 15%). The number of research outputs which were sole-authored by a person who could be identified as migrant or an ethnic minority were 39, that is almost 19% of the total. 26 of these were sole-authored projects and 13 were collaborative projects where an MME author took the lead.

4.2 Positioning of the authors

4.2.1 Sociodemographics of the authors

Figure 17 shows the breakdown of all authors and MME authors by gender (in this section authors includes any persons who authored and/or co-authored outputs). It clearly shows that there has been more female involvement in this area than males. Overall, 60% of persons who authored or co-authored the outputs included in this review were female and 40% were male. However, when we look at the MME authors and co-authors by gender, female involvement rises to 75% with MME males accounting for just 25% of contribution.

Figure 17 Authors by gender

The three figures below indicate the differences over time of publications authorship by female academics. Female academics racialised as other-than-‘white’ (indicated in orange) had sole authorship primarily for dissertations, no lead authorship in collaborative projects, and less co-authorship.

Figure 18 Female sole authors

Figure 19 Female first authored collaborations

Figure 20 Female co-author only

When considered by the authors who themselves are either migrants and/ or ethnic minorities (including those locally born), these were 52 authors who produced research outputs within the dataset. The majority of authors in this grouping were women (38/52 or 73%), of which 12 were racialised as other-than-‘white’ (just under a third). However, 12 of the 26 sole authored outputs were produced by females (under half), and of those 6 were produced by females racialised as other-than-‘white’, of which all were dissertations produced by PhD candidates. Females in the role of lead authors of collaborative outputs were 8 (of 13), with no females racialised as other-than-‘white’ leading collaborative outputs. Sole authorship for females racialised as other-than-‘white’ is very low. Note that in Figures 21 and 23, the acronym POC is used as a shorthand for those people racialised as other-than-‘white’, as these were designed before feedback provided on the draft report. Refer to Appendix A for more.

Figure 21 Single authorship by academic migrants and/ or ethnic minorities, differentiating females and those racialised as other-than-'white'

As indicated in Figure 21, 20 of these were people racialised as other-than-'white' (indicated as 'POC'). Of the 26 who sole authored outputs, 7 were dissertations. Of these sole authored outputs, 9 were by people racialised as other-than-'white' and 6 of the dissertations by people racialised as other-than-'white'. Females racialised as other-than-'white' only sole-authored dissertations. Thus, only 17 outputs were single authored by either migrants or people racialised as other-than-'white', of which people racialised as other-than-'white' specifically produced 4.

39 were engaged in collaborative research, of which 12 involved people racialised as other-than-'white'. 26 of these authors were listed as co-authors in non-lead author roles, of which 11 were people racialised as other-than-'white'. In terms of lead authors for collaborative projects, there were 13 migrants or ethnic minority as authors in this role, of which only 1 was a person racialised as other-than-'white'. Thus, leadership of collaborative co-authored outputs by migrant academics is low, as is leadership by academics racialised as other-than-'white'.

Figure 22 The date range of the authoring by migrant/ minority academics

Figures 22 and 23 visualise the increasing authorship by academics are migrants and academics racialised as other-than-‘white’ over time. It should be noted that of the academics sole authoring in the 2005-2010 date range, 2 were PhD dissertations; in 2011-2016 2 were dissertations of which one was by an academic racialised as other-than-‘white’; and 2017-2022, 4 were dissertations, all by academic citizens racialised as other-than-‘white’.

Figure 23 The date range of authoring by academics racialised as other-than-‘white’

4.2.2 Ethics, reflexivity and positionality of authors

Ethical considerations were written about in 32 projects. 21 of these were almost exclusively about ethical clearance or assurances of ethical conduct, with the remaining 11 discussing more substantive concerns about ethical principles, engagement, power or quagmires negotiated.

‘Positionality’ describes the positioning of researchers in relation to the subject of the research, and participants or context. It is a way in which to make visible to readers issues of the power, entitlements, and privileges of research participants and how this was managed by researchers, in addition to how they may have dealt with sensitive or difficult issues that arose during the research process. It also highlights the ways in which such positionality may have enriched the research relationships or insights. In many disciplines it has become an expected norm within academic publications, especially where the subject relates to the politics of representation.

In this study, it was found that out of the total 149 projects reviewed, only 7 included reflections on the researchers’ positionality. This was a surprisingly low amount – less than 5% of the studies – considering that the most of those falling within the population groups would be considered ‘vulnerable’ or at risk in some ways. This raises a number of questions.

It may suggest that more attention should be given to understanding and acknowledging researchers' positionality to ensure that researchers are self-critical, and that decisions and dynamics of the research process are made explicit to readers. Or it may point to a context where techno-rationality is most dominant, and where researchers operate under the illusion that the projection of objectivity as omniscientists would be a way for their findings to be better received by various audiences within a divisive context. The function of academic knowledge production was described as a source with more force or impact than other forms of knowledge production, particularly that produced from lived experience of non-academic groups. Thus, the legitimacy of objectivity is a currency with which academic publications operate in that context.

4.3 Constructions of identities and social categories

Language is recognised as having significant impacts on that which it describes. As such, we considered the ways in which the heterogenous individuals and social groups were constructed and characterised in the outputs. We found that there were many constructions of those commonly referred to as 'migrants' and 'ethnic minorities' in the Northern Irish context. Of interest was how these groups were referred to within the studies, and which groups specifically were named, and which omitted. Both the terms used and how often they occurred in the reviewed research items are outlined in this section.

A search was made for terms related to people seeking asylum and those with refugee status. A sizeable proportion of the research items used the terms 'refugee' and 'asylum seeker'. Overall, almost 11% of all projects referenced 'asylum seekers' and just over 11% mentioned 'refugees'. However, as almost all of the projects referred to both terms, and as such the percentage of projects which focused on these social groups overall was 11% of the total number of projects produced. There were 17 projects (with 23 outputs) which mentioned 'asylum seekers' and 18 projects (with 20 outputs) which referenced the term refugees. The differences between the two terms are important for the reader to bear in mind, as there are different rights and protections afforded those who have been granted refugee status compared to those seeking asylum. Not at all the outputs were cognisant of such delineations.

We also found that the ways in which migration, ethnicity, race, and minority groups were referred to in the research varied considerably, and not always with clear rhyme or reason.

Firstly, when it came to those who had migrated to Northern Ireland, in the outputs the most common term used was 'migrants' (35). Variations on this and associated terms included 'immigrants' (3), 'migrant communities' (2), 'migrant workers' (2), 'undocumented workers' (2), 'international workers' (1) and 'migrant worker communities' (1). The link between the issue of labour, employment and migration is thus one made within a number of the studies, as it is in state discourses. There is a politicised discourse around economic migrants compared to those seeking asylum in Northern Ireland.

Figure 24 National identities of participants per research output

We found specific groupings categorised according to national identity, which did not necessarily correlate with citizenship, passports or place of birth. In terms of the data analysed, we found that many of these appeared in more than one output. For the purposes of analysis in Figure 24, the amount of outputs that names each grouping is identified. Double migrant identities were not noted in the studies.

The 'Chinese' grouping were by far the most researched group in the data set, being mentioned in 53 outputs in total. It was not always clear whether they were from mainland China, Hong Kong or of Chinese origin from other countries, or which generation was being referred to. This matters because this is one of the 'communities' that have been the longest non-island born of all the ethnic minorities in Northern Ireland. The indigenous Irish Traveller grouping was named in 35 outputs, as were those Polish. The 'Indian' group were named in 31, against most often without a sense of the historic specificity, ancestry, or differences between those who would make up 'Indian' in Northern Ireland. Intersectional analysis of census data shows that this is a heterogeneous group, coming from both India itself, Pakistan and various post-colonial contexts as double migrants; and as with the Chinese grouping, some have been in the devolved nations for generations. Those named as Lithuanians were the subject of 23 research projects.

Then there are number of studies which researched social groups from (or descended from) the continent of Africa, principally Sudanese (18), Somali (15), Nigerian (13) and Zimbabwean (10) of which many were named within the same projects. Reporting did not always make the rationale informed the groupings explicit. In the report-and-respond discussions, it was suggested that the prevalence of certain nationalities from the continent of Africa may be due to the researchers' established relations, the ease of access to certain NGOs which represented or had access to those communities or the willingness of certain NGOs or communities to engage. This reflection is because it is peculiar that such groups are more represented in research when their numbers

are not in the majority African populations in Northern Ireland. The most recent 2021 census results show that the largest group of foreign-born Africans are South Africans and then Nigerians.

It is also possible that racialisation within Northern Ireland is reinscribed by funding calls, researchers and charities, who construct those 'in need' and therefore as valid or 'worthy' subjects for benevolent or philanthropic projects. It is possible that the lack of insider knowledge about such 'communities' within Northern Ireland, and the historical knowledge of the countries of origin, is reflected in the selection criteria and homogenising or blanketing of identities and generations within the host context. This is reflected in the prevalence of terms used in the outputs applied when referring to minoritised and/or racialized groups as a general category. These were 'minority ethnic groups' (21), 'ethnic minorities' (17), 'Black' (9), 'Black African' (8), 'minority ethnic communities' (8), 'BAME' (3), 'BME' (2), 'minority ethnic people' (2), 'minority groups' (2), 'diverse groups' (1), 'dual heritage' (1), 'ethnic groups' (1), 'minority ethnic' (1). This may have been affected by the fluctuations and lack of clarity which characterises legislative approaches to such nomenclature (see Appendix A).

There were intersecting identities and systems of social stratification identified in the studies. Equality Law in Northern Ireland has 9 'protected characteristics' which are named as such for public bodies to take steps to protect social groups from harm (see the 'context' section of this report). The outputs which used such terms included those which identified participants' 'age' (24), 'religion' (10), 'LGBT/Sexuality' (9), 'disability' (8). Figure 24 visualises the most prevalent national identities of participants within the studies. However, the most common intersection in outputs was 'gender' (46), which most often was to distinguish the participants' sex as male or female. This is not unexpected as it is the most actively legislated characteristic within public bodies in the UK.

The 'education' (8) of participants, their 'socio-economic' (8) status or background, and whether they were 'first-generation' (3) featured in some of the studies. Individual participants were also identified as 'children' (20), 'students' (3), 'young people' (3) or those with family (10).

Conclusion

This summary outlined and visualised aspects of the analysis of the research projects and outputs recorded on the institutional repositories of two research-intensive institutions. The visualisations enable identifying patterns and problematics about such research. Further analysis will be undertaken of the qualitative aspects of the outputs.

What was missing from the outputs was discussion of the research mechanisms, bureaucracy, and relations. These are some of the grey areas of research production. Some of these considerations, and others specific to the authors' intentionality, experiences and careers, were highlighted in the data generated with participating authors of these projects, as outlined in the next part of this section.

PART B: FINDINGS OF CONTENT ANALYSIS GENERATED FROM AGENTS OF RESEARCH PRODUCTION IN NORTHERN IRELAND

The following is a summary of the findings following a content analysis of the interview transcripts of 32 of the 247 authors, 3 members of one non-governmental organisation, and 2 officers involved in research development in NI universities. The analysis of the research outputs, as discussed in Part A, established that this is a marginal area of local enquiry.

Stop-starts that characterised participants' experiences of the research life-cycle are presented first in this section, to set the scene (1). Providing insights into their experiences of the contextual research landscape and cultures, participants' accounts revealed insights into the enablements and constraints for both such research and its impact (2 and 3). They also provided reflections on the ways in which this research topic was perceived by various interested parties (4) including public bodies in NI, NGOs, the general public, MME groups/individuals, within their institutions, the wider academic community/ies and the academic community in NI. They were also asked to reflect on how the studied groups are constructed (5)

Looking to how academics' desires, agency, career trajectory and life experiences influence their relation to these projects, questions were asked about their agency and experience as researchers within the Northern Irish academy. Data related to this revealed how the authors negotiated perceptions and discourses used in relation to the social groups they were studying (6); their personal and professional motivation for being engaged in such research (6.1) and, in turn, its impact on them (6.2). The last category summarised was data related to both their agency and their aspirations for the sustainability of this research area (6.3).

1. The research life cycle

Figure 25 Staggered research lifecycles for those who undertook more than 2 or only 1 project, as reported by participating authors

Participating authors described many stop-starts in the research cycle. Figure 25 visualises how participating authors experienced the conditions for the projects they undertook. The doughnut graphs show, from the centre out, the amount of projects for which funding was applied, and the amount awarded funding, and the amount either self- or unfunded. The black colour indicates the amount of academic publications. Following on from those projects, the authors were asked about their intentionality and processes of commencing further studies – the yellow and green shapes indicate how many intentions translated into proposals. There is a clear indication that those who worked on one project would not continue. As indicated by the lighter colours, much of the activity was only for the purposes of a single project. What is also interesting is the high amount of self- or unfunded investment by these authors in such research.

2. Enablements for research in NI

2.1 Enablements in general

As this is a marginalised area of enquiry, it is important to gain insights into how it was enabled. The authors were asked questions to provide data about their experiences and their responses are summarised outlined in this section.

- **Time-bound social change was perceived as an important driver for research in this area.** Demographic change, specifically an increasing migrant and minority ethnic population in NI; a corresponding forefronting of issues of race and racism in the public domain (accelerated by the labelling of Belfast as the 'race hate capital of the world'); and global social and cultural movements, for example, Black Lives Matter (BLM) increased interest at policy level and pressurised academia to respond. An existing interest in social cohesion in NI, due to the emphasis on conflict transformation in the region, has also facilitated research in this area.
- **The engagement and support of stakeholders, NGOs, academia and institutions were considered of importance in facilitating research in this area.** The willingness of schools and of other stakeholders to engage and participate in research, collaborating with NGOs, specifically migrant advocacy groups and local government supports were highlighted by a number of researchers as helpful. In academia, collaborations across faculty, disciplines and institutions were recognised as enabling factors in their research, as were institutional supports and recognition of projects.
- **Networks within and between institutions, connections established with non-academic community organisations and agencies, and relationships** grown from previous employments were considered beneficial by many authors. These networks facilitated conversations around the establishment of connections and potential collaborations; provided a support system to researchers who may have felt vulnerable or exposed in a research area that is sometimes seen as provocative and controversial; and importantly they served as gatekeepers to research participants who may otherwise have been reluctant to take part in the research.
- **Funding was considered to be enabling.** Indeed, some insisted that the research could not have taken place without it. As outlined in the funding section of this report (Part A.2), financial support came from a range of sources and also differed considerably in the breadth of its coverage.
- **Personal factors were enablements for their research.** Intrinsic interest; solidarity; flexibility (on the part of the researcher and others); location (being in the right place at the right time); practical support from family or friends; and support from mentors, colleagues and supervisors, were all mentioned as being important to facilitating research.
- **Academic autonomy and academic freedom.** A few of the established academics expressed how these rights granted them the space and latitude to express themselves critically as described in the quote below.

The other thing is that universities allow academic freedom, and there are very few institutions where it is possible to talk in the kinds of terms that I talk about racism. Universities have given me that opportunity to have a very strongly critical voice in a way that I simply wouldn't have in other institutions [UI2003].

2.2 Enablements for the impact of such research

Related to enablements, participants were asked to reflect on the ways in which the findings of such research (in particular if findings were significant for policy, practice or conceptual change,) were enabled. Their responses are summarised below. This should be read alongside the constraints of research impact.

- **Local stakeholders from the studied populations were identified as enabling of research impact.** Local minority ethnic groups were characterised as having agency, drive and stamina in advocating for the impact of the research. This is reflected in characterisations such as this one below, where the academic authors' reflections indicate admiration.

... probably the reason that worked was because the woman who was helping to facilitate that organisation is incredibly well connected and incredibly motivated and she somehow always makes things happen. And not just her, the women themselves... they've learnt how to advocate for themselves... they are already very inventive in finding ways to survive the crap that they deal with, but they learned other ways too. [UI1020]

In particular, respondents highlighted how public representatives from migrant and ethnic minority groups facilitated impact by putting issues on political and public agendas. Similarly, NGOs facilitated direct access to Stormont to address committee for ethnic minorities. It was articulated that specifically migrant and ethnic minority advocacy groups, which made it easier to 'see and feel' [UI1018] the level of impact. Those who were involved in activism-academic type participation models felt those successfully impacted specific minority ethnic communities, albeit within the limitations of what this participant articulates:

I've seen organizations... achieve wins. Not, you know, society-wide transformational change but micro ones, for specific communities affected... I don't want to overstate the change, but I've watched that be very effective as a model, if it's resourced to allow it to happen. [UI1003]

- **The engagement of public bodies was cited.** Some of the projects commissioned by public bodies had been designed to increase the amount and emphasis on the pathways to impact. Connections in the Executive office were supportive in getting findings out to the various interest groups. The promotion of findings and of research outputs in policies (such as the Education Authority and the Intercultural Education Service) were validating. Particular practitioner groups, such as those within participating schools (particularly those with existing connections to NGOs), were interested in findings and were eager to communicate them to a wider

audience. Wider than the local, links with authoritative international bodies such as UNESCO was seen as of value, because it drew attention for funding impact events and promotion. The small size of NI and respect according to universities, was identified as an enablement for those who had increased impact through direct contact with politicians.

- **Academic research support and allies were seen as essential for many.** This included practical support and encouragement from institutional initiatives and training, particularly those to do with research impact.
- **Both academic and wider networks were included in enablements for impact.** Some of the authors had found that utilising international academic networks facilitated the promotion of NI issues. Others found that connections with academics doing cognate research facilitated conversations around impact and sometimes even those contacts facilitated different avenues to disseminate the findings.
- **Funding increased the capacity and generated desire for public engagement.** With the 'impact agenda' having been quantified in UK research assessments, more recent research has benefited from small pots of money for impact activities, interventions, impact training and the development of outputs.
- **The media and various forums of communication.** Media reports had raised awareness among researchers, and appetite for funders. Institutional engagement with media was also cited as enabling impact and promotion of research.

3. Constraints on such research in NI

3.1 Constraints in general

The volume of research in this area in NI has been remarkably low. It is unsurprising then that the authors revealed a significant number of constraints, barriers or problematics when attempting to do this type of research. Some of these are outlined here.

- **Time bound social and economic disruptions and changes were highlighted as significant.** The economic crash following the Celtic Tiger through to Covid, constraints spanned the length of duration that researchers had been involved in such enquiry, and more recent dynamics. These impacted public interest, access to participants, reduced funding, and mobility issues in general. Many spoke about these as existing factors that had recently been compounded by Brexit, which they saw as having huge ramifications for research in this area in NI. Furthermore, the escalation of race-based tensions into public culture wars (for instance, the rejection of Critical Race Theory both in the US and in the UK and the shifting

political landscape in NI), were cited as influenced that militated against certain kinds of conversations about race, ethnicity and migration in the region.

- **The lack of recognition or value for this research area in NI.** Some authors claimed that in general issues pertaining to minority ethnic communities are regarded as 'extra' or a 'side-show'. The majority of researchers undertaking it were 'outsiders' to the dominant in-groups (as indicated by the self-identification visualised in Figure 4, p.14), and thus had not been socialised to dismiss the local groups. Of concern is that their personal commitment to research the issues was constrained within generally unfavourable conditions. Some authors found that NGOs and some religious organisations were reluctant to engage due to citing a lack of interest, time and/or resources; a divergence with their prioritised topics of interest; or from research fatigue. This was not only a dynamic outside the university - quite a few authors relayed a lack of interest and/or support from their institutions in NI, which they had experienced was starkly contrasted with attitudes toward this research in other UK universities. One researcher highlighted how she felt her research in this area was simply 'tolerated in NI rather than encouraged.

Tolerant, I would say. I think tolerant is the word I would use. It was tolerated as long as it didn't interfere with the teaching and as long as I could assure them that there would be journal articles and grant money coming from it.
[UI2003]

- **Academic identity/positionality was limiting for migrant academics.** As many of the researchers were 'outsiders', they found that lacking connections and creating networks proved challenging for some, particularly in relation to accessing research participants and also being exposed to sectarian tensions.
- **The Troubles legacies overshadowed other conflicts or areas of enquire.** The overwhelming emphasis on legacy issues in NI, meant that issues of ethnicity are still very much focused on the local divisions of nationalism and unionism. This was very often much to the detriment of other research as reported by this author:

So you know it's become this sort of homunculus sort of category which just basically, I'm thinking, it's just not left any space for anything else [UI1004]

Funding, too, was prioritised or directed towards Protestant/Catholic relations. This was stated by almost all the participating authors. With much research, particularly in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (but in others too), the most valued focus of the institutions and many of the leading academics was on the divisions and relations of the majority populations, and indeed various hubs of research and the careers of many revolved around that. The currency of academic capitalism in the area was on the legacies of conflict in the local context, mirroring the 'dark tourism' prevalent in NI. While many of the participating authors comprehended why this was so, and had even produced related knowledge, they felt there was

little space allowed within the competition of resources. One of the ways around this, was where research linked the two.

- **Methodological barriers were identified.** These included the inadequacy of existing data and data gaps when it came to quantitative data collected by public bodies, and barriers to access. The fact that the populations under study are minorities was also cited as a constraint for such research, with often too small numbers, particularly if for primary data engagement and for intersectional or focused analysis. Some authors mentioned that there was often a lengthy and complicated ethics application process for accessing public data and for working with MME people as they were presumed to be, sometimes erroneously, vulnerable. This led to significant delays. In a number of cases the difficulties related to this issue discouraged further research in the local context.
- **Funding was not readily available.** In a highly competitive environment, the chances of being awarded research funding for such projects was seen as slim. Triangulated perceptions from the participating authors, research development officers and members of the NGO were similarly assertive in their thinking that funders lacked interest in this area and chose to invest in 'safer' research studies. Indeed, they claimed there was a lack of interest in funding research in NI in general. One of the participants from the non-academic partner expressed their perceptions about what those in power chose, when there was a conflict of interest:

And then again as well, funders during crises, they prioritise and once again we are not anyone's priority. That's what happens. [NGO001]

- **Funding, when granted, was found to be insufficient and limited in its coverage.** One participant described the implications of this on the mechanics of the research process.

I mean the money on these projects is hardly worth talking about, and you know it can feel very stretched when you have to do things with research assistants and transcription and so on [UI1013]

These conditions encouraged researchers to jump quickly from project to project. They prioritised the 'deliverables' promised to the funders, which meant they may have not been enabled to follow up on that not contractually obligated, whether that was academic dissemination or impact outputs/activities.

- **The research culture and environment were regarded as challenging by many of the authors.** NI was recognised as a marginal space that operated with a lack of transparency or plurality for those who operated outside of dominant norms or groups. It was seen to be a hierarchical research culture that was misogynistic, patriarchal and racist. The capitalist academic system was seen to promote commercially driven research, even if billed as 'social'. For some, it was 'a very unpleasant power-driven REF based culture of threat' with an over reliance on the

'publish or perish scenario' [RD001]. Some authors found that there was a lack of openness, a bias against non-English speakers and disadvantaged outcome for females who were also migrants or identified as ethnic minorities.

3.1 Constraints on the impact of such research

Where findings were found to be of value, what were the barriers, constraints or problematics in terms of trying to affect impact of those in Northern Ireland? Some of the issues the authors encountered related to this aspect of their research are outlined here.

- **Disruptions such as the suspension of Stormont, the economic crisis of mid-2000s and Covid19.** With many of the participants and lobbyists coming from, or needing connections with voluntary work contributions and precarious findings, societal disruptions adversely impacted the pathways to impact. Not having governance in Stormont seemed to affect the entire research ecology. A number of researchers indicated that the restrictions imposed during Covid significantly constrained the impact of their research. Generally due to the shutdown of public spaces, lack of mobility and lockdowns resulted in organisations pulling back and ultimately also shutting down, which prevented presentation and dissemination of findings. This may also have had an impact on the continuation of work, and the drop on the output since 2020.
- **Lack of interest or engagement from public bodies.** This resulted in barriers to promotion of frameworks, models and sharing of findings. It was felt that institutional support in this research area globally was good, but not in relation to NI specifically.
- **Lack of interest or engagement from NGOs.** Authors articulated that for many NGOs, the focus was in a different direction to these populations. For those NGOs which did specialise or were peopled by migrants and/or ethnic minorities, their research fatigue was highlighted by a number of researchers, who described that they found NGOs drained, finding research extractive, and with little capacity to engage. This was confirmed by the members of the NGO who engaged in the report-and-respond process. In the excerpt below, a participating author shared what she learnt in an exchange with an organisation,

I got a response from one organisation and I don't know if this person did it deliberately. But I said in the subject header of the e-mail 'PhD research', and she changed it to 'volunteering'. And then I got a response [when the gatekeeper sent it out]. Because I was giving something to them. And I don't know whether that was deliberate, or maybe she was just saying, 'well you know, I'll clarify this'. So community organisations don't have a lot of staff, they don't have a lot of extra capacity and they don't want a researcher and lots of researchers are saying, 'I want to come to you and I want to take from you'. [UI1019]

While this was understood, the capacity of academic staff to provide such investment of their time limited the possibilities of such exchange.

- **Publication on NI raised challenges.** To successfully publish research on NI, many of the participating authors explained that the study had to be framed as not specifically about NI, particularly in high- ranking journals. Funders sometimes demanded input into publication requirements around findings which also affected impact. The participating research development officers also reflected that the REF system could be unhelpful in this regard, as it can be in tension with local, situated, small scale impact activities and/or outputs. Moreover, the interpretation of REF as contributing to career security or progression, could be those within the Units of Assessment from inter-disciplinary work, or heads of department from dissuading researchers from undertaking work that might put them at risk of less funding and/or less high 'international' rating. REF was raised in a number of participants' responses, specifically around impact.

There are very strict parameters around what can count for REF evidence whereas in practice it doesn't really work like that. It could be that somebody engages with the policy maker and they don't do anything with it and then five years later the topic arises and so soon we're chatting about. So much depends on external circumstances and then they remember back, or get back in contact or use something from years ago, it's not a sort of linear process in reality. So it's a very imperfect system - there's no good way to measure impact because it is so complicated [RD001]

- **Commissioned or funding grant-driven research inhibits implementation of findings.** As is demonstrated in the funding award section of the report (see p.24), funders seemed to give preference and enablements towards certain outputs.
- **Time was cited as a constraint.** A number of the participating authors and the research development officers, mentioned time was a constraint. This included the poor timing and short turnaround of calls for funding for such projects to finding the time to develop and disseminate outputs for impact.

4. Perceptions of this research in NI

Participants were asked if they had any sense of how academic research in this area might be valued by policy makers, those in positions of power, those within civil society groups and indeed whether it is appreciated by the general public. They were also asked how the academic communities in NI responded. Below their responses are organised per stakeholder, and one can see differing experiences as is to be expected of projects with different publics, on varied topics and led by different researchers.

- **General public.** Researchers described this as 'a highly charged area of study' that "reflects their general prejudice against other people' [UI1010]. For the most,

researchers felt there was not a dominant public response, and that the perceptions of the public were 'split down the middle' [UI1002] or 'a very mixed bag' [UI1010]. Predictably, some of the general public who expressed an opinion on their research felt that money would be better spent researching 'local issues' (meaning majority communities), and others felt that as the populations were a minority, they were not important. However, there were some who felt that it made sense to research this area as the numbers of migrants and minority ethnic persons had increased significantly.

- **Public bodies in NI.** Authors highlighted a lack of awareness of migrant needs among public officers was compounded by a lack of action in same. It was felt that many remain stuck on 'green and orange' politics. Such officers claim that small numbers of migrants and ethnic minorities do not warrant research and are defensive and reluctant to engage. On the other hand, some of the academic authors found a selection of public officials interested and supportive.
- **NGOs.** Some authors noted a significant appetite for this research among NGOs who perceived it as urgent, and with them the research garnered a lot of support and attention. This is reflected in the response below.

... there's different types of NGOs. So, some of the small scale ones that might have helped give me access to migrants for instance. They were motivated to help with the research because they felt it was going to deal with some of the structural problems that they were seeing on a daily basis. So that was their motivation. It was a bit different. It was kind of clearly altruistic. [UI1011]

Research that was well received and lauded as valuable, was when it was used for evidence-based interventions. However, on the other hand, participating authors felt that some NGOs were dismissive, displayed a negative view of academics, or believed the research was irrelevant or lacked efficacy. This was confirmed by the participating members of an NGOs, who stated that they had research fatigue and were frustrated with the impact of such research, as they felt they were being asked the same questions as 10 years ago and that no demonstrable changes had taken place.

- **Groups and individuals from the studied populations.** Some of the participating authors and members of the NGO described significant research fatigue among these groups, who could see no tangible benefit in taking part in research and so became increasingly reluctant to engage again and again. The lack of an effective mechanism for disseminating many different types of beneficial findings and supports across heterogeneous groups and organisations was outlined as a disservice to these groups.

- **Wider academic community.** On the one hand, participating authors found that the international academic communities were universally positive, who sometimes even praised such research and saw local responsiveness as necessary and ethical practice in a transitioning society. On the other, peer reviewers of funding and publications were described as diminishing the value of the research, feeling it had limited crossover value, was not of international interest or simply miscomprehended the race/ ethnicity situation in NI in general.
- **Academic community in NI.** Participating authors expressed how research in this area does not have the same prestige as conflict related, transitional justice work. Where it was seen as most problematic was where it related to challenging the established claims of those local academics whose work was on the local conflict, particularly for participating authors who had linked their findings to the colonial legacy. Many spoke about the marginality of the subject, and how that was reflected in various ways in their institutions, including the formal curricula. Some described a begrudging attitude of local academics to the subject, with a concern of 'let's look after our own groups first', and 'there's so few of them, just let them get on with it'. Some of the authors recognised positive interest and support, particularly those newer to the research area; however, many saw such interest as most often superficial.

5. Academics' negotiations of constructions of and discourses about social groups in NI

Participants were asked to reflect on the ways in which they experienced individuals from social groups categorised as 'ethnic minorities' and 'migrants' in Northern Ireland are constructed, and in what ways this impacted their research. This should be read against the analysis of the positioning of the studied groups within the research outputs (see Part A.4.1). Questions were raised about the authors' agency in terms of the politics of representation when presenting their research to various audiences at the different points of the research cycle. Responses have been grouped into representations and discourses within policy and practice exogenous; by the academic communities and researcher positionality.

- **Imprecise and often incorrect categories and data collection.** While existing data was useful to an extent, they were not always explicit which at times resulted in limitations in the quality of the data. This is clearly outlined in this author's experience of the difficulties faced when publishing on the research.

So I mean part of our difficulty [when publishing] was we were trying to frame it as this particular group but the data points weren't always explicit about that. It kind of goes back to the point where you could tie it into the fact that [the existing dataset is] limited, you can't ask all the questions. And then it goes back to a numbers game and you won't necessarily get a lot of detailed questions from a particular group if that group isn't large

enough to warrant particular questions about more broader questions like could kind of go into a lot of different aspects [UI1018]

- **Distinctions between categories.** Examples cited of this were the distinctions between refugee vs asylum seeker; migrant vs ethnic minority; BAME vs white; newcomer, native vs non-native etc. Authors outlined challenges when encountering such separations. For example, the confusion between refugees and asylum seekers when they are very distinct legal situations can make it 'tricky' for research and its impact, it affects the quality of the research as their rights and conditions are very different. The limitations of data collected within the categories 'BAME' and the obstacles when extrapolating data using this separation was highlighted. As was the othering aspect of the 'newcomer' label as well as its inappropriate application in many institutions in NI, when providing supports for those speaking languages other than English, such as schools.
- **The use of the term 'community' in NI.** The word which carries a lot of historical weight in NI as it references the two majority communities – nationalist and unionist. Construction of 'new' communities was seen to then further 'lump' individuals with very different histories and characteristics in one group or new groups not of their choosing or identification. Authors highlighted that discourse around 'community' rarely involved critical interrogation of positions of power. This construction of community results in demands and limitations being placed on people due to membership of a community or representation of certain characteristics.
- **Constructions of minority groups was highlighted as often not aligned with the preference of the authors nor studied participants.** They were constructed as vulnerable, lacking agency, deprived or deficit, associated with a negative discourse and framing, and sometimes stereotyped. At other times, positive framing was 'good' or model citizens, or exoticised, or useful for reflecting 'our experiences' or seeing 'our' problems with fresh eyes, or in ways that frame those making changes as overly benevolent. There was a general agreement that such constructions were often erroneous and should be challenged appropriately whenever possible. Nonetheless, some researchers found they were co-opted into such framing of these groups when making applications for funding or support. Authors argued that it should be possible and encouraged to frame concerns in ways that are accessible and understandable without necessarily having to resort to standard tropes or discourses.
- **Researcher self-criticality.** Participating authors reflected varying capacity for self-reflection and desire for such discussion. Many of those who identified as 'white' and from the Global North, expressed more questioning of their legitimacy to undertake such study. When triangulated with the analysis of the published outputs, there are indications that this is an issue of unease and omission. Unusual for research of such power imbalance, there were very few written reflections

recorded within the published outputs about researcher positionality and ethical considerations.

6. Authors' reflections on their involvement in such research

6.1 Academics' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for undertaking the research

Internal motivation is often understood as an individual phenomenon, with the degree of motivation depending on how the individual perceives a particular task, activity or assignment (Katz, 2005). Some argue that researchers choose their career path out of sheer curiosity in order to improve their understanding of the world, make new discoveries or utilise them to benefit society (Joynson & Leyser, 2015). However, researchers are not autonomous. Prior research about research in NI have pointed to the politics of research production both during the Troubles and in the peace-negotiations period (D. C. Irwin, 2005; Taylor, 1987, 1988). In their responses, the participating authors reflected on how motivation was psychosocial, with varied influences and motivations, including from within and beyond the university.

The authors interviewed in this study outlined a range of factors which motivated them to carry out research about migrant and minority ethnic groups in Northern Ireland. These motivating factors have been categorised into three areas. The first was academic motivation. Responses included within this category was that the subject related to their disciplinary and/or methodological tradition; that it was an extension of the academic research and/or work they had previously carried out; and, in some instances, due to employment opportunities that were presented.

The second category was related to their interest in social change. In accordance with Joynson and Leyser (2015), participants' responses indicated that such interest in social change, social forces and dynamics in general was a motivator for undertaking such research. For some there was a particular focus on the phenomenon of Northern Ireland migrants. Social justice was frequently referred to as an important driving factor in researchers' motivation for undertaking this research. The excerpt below is an example of the type of response from an author that was responding as an outsider to the social groups under study:

*Just in the streets of Belfast and around the place you saw that there were migrant communities and people of colour who lived here and have established lives in Northern Ireland but they didn't really seem to be talked about at all. And it was almost as if they were just sort of peripheral to this framework of two communities. So when I was at undergrad level I started to get kind of a bit interested in this. What's the background to this? Where do people from migrant minority ethnic backgrounds fit into society?
[U11012]*

A number of the researchers who took part in this study expressed that motivation was often personal in nature. When discussing the 'personal', some described having

received substantial support or encouragement from colleagues and mentors to undertake the research. Quite a few mentioned that they were motivated by their own personal interest in the area; or that their identity, their background, life or work experiences had influenced their choices to engage in such research. Many expressed feeling a sense of personal obligation or commitment to research issues related to migrant and minority ethnic persons. For these, their ethical consciousness was an important factor. A number of the authors who felt such intrinsic motivation, articulated their desire to practice as engaged intellectuals (Bell & Lewis, 2022). This is indicated in the excerpt below, where the academic practice of writing to both disseminate knowledge and effect impact is articulated by this academic:

I think it's an area I'm particularly passionate about and I've engaged in lots of different ways both in practical kind of directly engaged ways as well as scholarly. And it's something I'm trying to do more with my writing. That my writing stands the gamut in terms of, okay producing the scholarly work, but also being able to contribute to policy. But also kind of writing more publicly about it. So trying to aspire to doing all of those things because I think it's important to communicate what it is that we're doing here [UI1013].

Finally, there were also a number of people who mentioned that their involvement in the research came about by accident or coincidence. This included those where unintentional findings of a project, or an issue related to ethnic minorities or migrants in NI.

6.2 The impact of such research on the researcher

When it came to questions about the impact of the research, the impacts of involvement by the participating authors were often described in terms of the difference made to the research itself and/or knowledge, the participants and less frequently on the researchers themselves. In this study, the impacts on the research environment, on policy and support for 'local' groups, the development of resources and workshops are all outlined as important outcomes of the research projects the researchers have been involved in. However, how the research or that process impacted the researchers themselves was the primary interest in this study. The main impacts reported by the authors fell generally into two categories, the first was how it impacted them in a professional capacity, how it affected their career, positively or no impact. They were asked how it influenced their intellectual thinking, research approach and perspective, and what insights they gleaned from it. They outlined the impacts it had on their teaching and emphasised the important networks they developed as a result of carrying out this research.

I guess the reason why I'm saying this is that was a really good moment for me to mobilise this network and that network whilst we didn't get the funding, in a sense all of the research I was doing that was being funded by X [funder] and others allowed me to participate and mobilise that network and other stuff has come out of that. So you know, that sort of, I

guess projected me a little bit into that European dimension which is just a bit more interesting than you know, keeping it more parochial. [UI1011]

The second category was how the research impacted the researchers in a personal capacity. They outlined how it affected their sense of belonging and wellbeing, how they navigated the insider/outsider phenomenon and the exclusion that it sometimes generated. At times, pursuing this area of research led to frustration, disappointment, and on occasion to secondary trauma experienced by the researchers. On a more positive note, some reflected that it had led to feelings of accomplishment, growth and confidence as their identities within the country and as academics, developed through the engagements. Below is the reflection of one of the authors:

Northern Ireland for me it was a very interesting one because it pushed me further than I'd been pushed before... do I know enough about the local culture and the local situation to make sense of this and if I do, what is the most valuable way in which I can contribute, the expert knowledge but also the skills that I have in this context? [UI2003]

6.3 Participants authors' agency and desire to contribute to creating a more sustainable knowledge-base

One of the more concerning findings of the analysis of research outputs was that there were actually very few researchers engaged in this work in Northern Ireland, and that only a small amount of those saw this as central to their work, with the majority producing a single output. Attrition of the few productive researchers would have a significant impact on the already small amount of research on this topic. This is reflected in the research lifecycles (Figure 25). Therefore, an important question posed to the authors was about the sustainability of research in this area. Probing questions included: *how have they generated work or dialogue or thinking about such research within the academic community? What inroads have been made in terms of motivating early career academics, infusing such research within their teaching modules, or creating an interest for people to do research in the area?*

Responses to this issue from participating authors were mostly aspirational 'best' practices. Participants would offer their opinions of what 'should' be happening to make this a sustainable research area. The interviewer often had to reorient them to reflect directly on their own agency, the ways in which it was enacted, and the limits to its enactment.

The establishment of networks and research hubs were cited as crucial in the sustainability of this research in Northern Ireland. However, as this respondent observed, this was as yet not a feature of the research landscape in NI:

I'm just aware that everybody's working in quite small little pockets in Northern Ireland and I think it would be a great kind of great thing if people could harness their abilities and take that and move forward at times in some directions. Because I think a lot of power comes from working with

others. And you know that the number of years I've worked it does seem to be people working in kind of silos often. [UI2001]

Many researchers related that networks in other countries, in particular other parts of the UK, provided invaluable support and encouragement to engage in this research. They were cited as important for encouraging collaborations and promoting visibility. Conferences, media engagements and the publication of research were also noted as being fundamental to this end.

Some of the researchers who were employed in contracts with teaching capacity, expressed that they enacted their agency primarily through their teaching. They did so by building their research into teaching modules, developing models and frameworks, and making data accessible. However, others felt that this was regarded by NI universities as a 'niche area' and they were unable to find space in the curriculum for it. The supervision of PhD students, and promotion or support of post-docs in the area, were recognised as being important in this regard. This was, however, dependent on the subject interest of their students or on funded calls, most of which were competitively awarded by the Department for the Economy. Only a single respondent had found that route productive, and from that created sustainable impact over years of supervision, curriculum-infusion and practitioner engagement. International doctoral authors who had chosen this area of research, who authored a number of the dissertations in the study's set, unfortunately left NI.

Some of the issues and obstacles to promoting and sustaining this work that respondents cited were institutional structural issues, and the precarity of the academic environment in general. Some also raised issues of the challenges for the pipeline to academia of students who are from migrant or ethnic minority social groups, and barriers to open employment for projects with small funding.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The triangulated analysis offers interpretations about the ways in which the academic research practice is shaped by, resists and/or negotiates various socio-cultural influences, enablements and constraints in local research ecologies.

1. Research-intensive universities are not responsive to changes in local socio-demographics

The study found that Northern Ireland's research-intensive institutions are not responsive to the changes in their local populations through the research function, effectively under-serving and undocumented the histories, perspectives, needs and accounts of ethnic minorities and migrants through academic knowledge production. Recorded on the institutions' Research Information Management Systems were 209 outputs related to this area of enquiry; compared to over 120 000 recorded outputs on other subjects.

The outputs were predominantly driven by incentives for an evidence-base to inform policy or services, funded by the NI government, public bodies or charities. Much of this falls under researching in service of societal need. However, much of the orientation did not necessarily aim to catalyse systemic change, nor provide holistic nor rich insights. Rather characterisation was of migrants and/or ethnic minority groups as a 'problem', deficit or in need; or as sources from which to extract specific information. Despite the majority of outputs being impact-related, the perception and experience of both participating authors and the members of the NGO, was that larger conditions rendered such research ineffectual. Efficacy, despite being a discourse underpinning much of the state-supported research, adversely impacted academic-community relations in this area.

As with political discourse, legislation and policy implementation about race and migration within NI over its history, this study found that deferral, over-looking and avoidance characterise much the same dynamics when it came to local interest in, investment and prioritisation of academic research about these groups; a pattern of unresponsiveness that continues to the present day. As a prior scholar of social science in the United Kingdom asked about the state of the 'blindspot' about ethnicity within NI, "should we expect something different from scholars?" (Gilligan, 2022, p. 4).

The consequences of such deficit are many. This lack of engagement leaves localised knowledges and perceptions about such minoritised groups open to continued

nonhistorical, decontextualised, unsupported, nonfactual, invented or imagined assumptions, stereotyping, othering and homogenising. It places the burden of knowledge making on non-academic individuals or groups; or those academics positioned outside of the locality. It reduces the potential of enriching methodological approaches across the local academic community through experiential exchange; and of building inter- and multi-disciplinary communities in the area of enquiry locally to internationally. Similarly, the potential of translation, through research-informed teaching within higher education institutions; and the reproduction of such knowledge at other levels of education within the country, is reduced.

2. Growth in the post-conflict period is present, but scholarly enquiry is marginal

There was marked growth in academic research about this area of enquiry. The outputs recorded on the institutional Research Information Management Systems (RIMS) were from 1994, with increases until the peak year of engagement in 2018, following which it seems to have dropped somewhat. However, at no given year were there ever as many as 25 outputs (including academic dissemination, and translation outputs) produced on this area in NI. Less than half the research outputs were for academic dissemination. Thus, the field cannot be said to be established within this context.

Production in this time frame has been sporadic and very much dependent on incentives outside of the institutions, or in rare cases, investment by a few dedicated individual academics to local populations. A few of the latter have created impressive input – securing doctoral funding, integrating the research and its findings into their teaching, establishing themselves as authorities in this area, and with that the growth of good relations with practitioner and participant communities. Recommendations to foster this area would be firstly validation of those with a track record of under-taking such research, and enablements to have them continue to grow, and to foster, interest in knowledge production in this area.

There should be recognition that there has been a double burden for the majority of the authors, as women and as migrants in a patriarchal, xenophobic context. The role of migrant academics to counter- or balance the omissions and provincialisation of local academics, has been noted in prior studies of academic science in Northern Ireland (Taylor, 1988). Addressing this hidden curriculum should be a primary concern for local institutions. Until such change, the encouragement through validation, incentives, rewards and funding opportunities in this area would undoubtedly increase interest and provide support.

3. Investment needed for the area of enquiry to grow and become sustainable

Triangulated data from this study, indicated that much more investment would be needed to make this a sustainable area of local enquiry. This includes both financial investment, in addition to research development and improving the research-teaching nexus.

3.1 Recommendation: Funding research about NI ethnic minorities and migrants

More funding calls and better funding of this research is required. This confirms prior analysis of the funding of NI research, and the argument that more plural research should be funded to address inequalities in society, rather than the dominance of funding for conflict-related research (Schubotz, 2005).

The SLR revealed that under 40% of the projects received partial or full funding. Most of the funding was by non-academic funders (with reports and journal articles), then academic funders (predominantly producing journal articles) or bodies connected to the NI government (predominantly producing reports). Funding by non-academic organisations and by the NI government produced the most outputs. 10 projects were funded by non-UK funding, and only one by UK government funding.

Interviews with participating authors and research officers revealed that funding of such research is an area to address. Funding is often limited and includes expectation of a high amount of non-academic outputs for investment. The mapping of research lifecycles indicated high levels of investment by the researchers to bridge funding gaps, which often disenchanted those who tried and then abandoned the area after the experience of one project.

Funding also did not always enable praxis: such as funds to recruit and reimburse participants, to train fieldworkers from the studied groups, to support precarious researchers to publish after the project terminated with a report, including doctoral students publishing post-graduation. Translation activities into curricula at school-level was under-funded, particularly translation into curricula at higher education level.

3.2 Recommendations for the academic communities

There is a need for more development of (and between) local researchers themselves operating across disciplines and institutions to share wisdom as a network and possibly collaborate. Interactions with those in other post-conflict or politically charged research environments, and those with experience in negotiating marginalised studies, would be of value for the reflexivity of such academics, and negotiating the tensions between academic freedom, academic autonomy and the politics of legitimacy.

Institutions and such networks could offer research development generally on the ethno-political implications of exclusion of minorities from local research. For researchers working in this area of enquiry, clearer understanding of the relation of terms to law and rights, and the problematics with deficit and benevolent discourses would be important. Because of the socio-cultural practices of the context, it seems that local researchers may also benefit from instruction on the ways in which to interact with non-majority populations.

The power of those asked to participate and the positioning of those subjected to such research should be altered to ensure the democratisation of the area of enquiry. There is a need to create a pipeline of local ethnic minorities into academic positions in this area of enquiry for intellectual leadership. Local ethnic minorities representation within the academic staff composition in NI is not monitored, and thus inequalities cannot be identified nor addressed.

There should be more attention to infusing curricula with research findings for the education of those from NI in higher education, and in turn in prior education and continuous professional development. Research on this is also needed.

4. Participation: Positioning and authorship

The study found that there was a high proportion of the outputs that included the participation of the people under study (with input into primary data generation), almost as much as those projects where they were the subject of study. This is a positive indication. When it came to the more powerful position of decision-making in research or the authoring of knowledge, this was rarely undertaken by local-born persons categorised as ethnic minorities, even as co-authors. With far more representation than their populations in NI universities, the majority of authors of these outputs were women and/or migrants. Few of the academics racialised as other-than-'white' led in such projects. Thus representation, participation and authorship are not as yet democratic in this context. Undertaking research in marginalised and under-valued areas carries the threat of loss in terms of career advancement, a cost to the private gains noted in women's research because they undertake more social engagement/ justice projects (Zhang & Sivertsen, 2021).

Outputs were mapped according to positioning of local ethnic minorities and migrants, the persons to whom such research enquiry relates, to see how that related to subject-object relations, attribution and authorship. This gave us a sense of the power relations within this context, and the authoring of such knowledge. It was found that the majority of outputs positioned such groups as subjects of study, then a comparable but less amount as participants in the studies. Far less (7) explicitly attributed involvement to named organisations (such as NGOs) as partners within the research. In terms of authorship, the critical review provided quantitative detail on the research outputs and authorship. This included which researchers have worked in this area; and the social location of such authors, including sex, ethnicity and migrant/ NI-born status; and their positioning in terms of sole/ first/ other authors. It was found that despite NI institutions having less female academic staff than male staff (and the

lowest composition of female staff in the UK), a majority of the authors of this research were female. This was the case too when considering the authors who were either migrants and/ or ethnic minorities, where the majority were again female. However, the lead author position was rarely a person racialised as other-than-'white', and particularly not a person racialised as other-than-'white' who was female. Intersecting systems of discrimination impacted academic authorship in this area of enquiry; despite the subject matter being about ethnic minorities.

5. Academic agency and writing between and across the lines

The study found that academic authors were mostly driven by intrinsic motivation and ethical commitments exogenous to the priorities and values of the NI institutions and its dominant publics. This was consistently the pattern for those who were staff members, and for many in research contracts and who had undertaken PhDs in the area. Professional incentives, such as short-term contracts or specific commissions/ funding calls, were more prevalently cited by those whose engagement was limited to one project, produced research reports or impact-activities, and those who were working in the last five years in short-term or precarious contracts. The increase of interest and attention to the area, precipitated by media attention around such communities, seemed to have made the area more attractive or pressing in the minds of some.

Many of the participating authors were cognisant and self-critical about how they negotiated different readership in the discourses they used, balancing pragmatic gains of funding and efficacy with ethics. Shared communication with audiences that had power to lead or implement change was a primary concern for publication of impact-related outputs, and in almost all cases this would be members of the majority groups who utilised often deficit discourses and incorrect or problematic terminology. Some authors admitted that much of what they produced was common knowledge to the participants anyway - the role of the output was the authorising of such claims. Thus, in those outputs they adopted discourses for pragmatic reasons, in the hopes of increasing the efficacy of research impact. Some even felt that the participants were well aware of the game and would not be affronted or offended by this form of code swapping. Similarly, in proposals and for funders' reports, authors would adopt or include discourses about the populations which increased their chances of being awarded funding, including that of 'crisis' or deficit to make the case more pressing, to gain attention or highlight aspects that they knew had currency with policy makers. This also impacted the subject matter itself, impoverishing more heterogenous studies and insights.

When it came to academic publications, there was more allowance for correct terminology expected with academic audiences. Some of the dilemma faced in those instances, were the 'speaking up' for the NI case to increase the perception that it was not too exceptional to be of interest to an international audience. This included making the decision to use 'UK' in the title or abstract, or post-conflict, or some other capital that the case had. Limitations to academic authors' agency

included how other stakeholders' would influence the nature of participation and positioning within the research, particularly in terms of assumptions of who were the beneficiaries and who were experts. Another dilemma was trying to explain problems in the quality of the data that was affected by NI's collection, curation and barriers to access data sets about the populations.

These discussions with the participating authors provide explanation, and some insight into why there was such a range of terms used within the outputs analysed (Part A 4.3). The outputs were intended for different audiences, as is reflected by the split between those that were for academic dissemination and those prepared as pathways to impact (Part A 1). However, incorrect terminology should be challenged, and steps taken to better inform non-academic audiences. Some of these have legal implications. Those that construct those they describe as deficit should also be challenged for both the adverse public perception this reproduces, and the effects of the labelled persons.

Participating authors expressed frustrations, and in some case restrictions on their academic freedoms within their institutions. The incorporation of findings into their teaching, the dissemination of such research to colleagues, the value of such research in promotion, the assumptions of ethical review boards, and the awarding of internal funding, were cited as limited by misrecognition of the value of such research. The ways in which they represented the socio-demographics under study seemed to be the primary consideration within this politics of academic practice. Not all of the authors were cognisant of such problematics nor of their role within such academic bureaucracy.

6. The function of academic knowledge production in what emerged as a technocratic, sectarian, racialised context

The publication of academic research was found to serve a number of dominant pre-defined functions within Northern Ireland; and these determined the ways in which the subject and related sociodemographic groups were constructed, the methods of output, and the constructions of the authors.

Academic knowledge was privileged above other knowledge production. It was constructed as not biased, partisan and above conflicts of interest. It is also constructed as more reliable, rigorous and representative than other sources. This is a strongly positivist and techno-rationalist understanding of academic knowledge; and a construction of the academic as omniscient. Prior research on this context suggests this has been a carefully crafted notion, by the state and its universities, to establish and maintain the legitimacy of academia in a divisive society (D. C. Irwin, 2005; Taylor, 1988). Against it is implicitly pitted the notion that ground-up knowledge production by non-authorised individuals or groups will be unreliable, partisan, political and at worse, irrational.

Much of the research seems to have been undertaken to address a societal question or provide an evidence-based to inform policy or practice. In one way, this was

interpreted by the participants as playing a potentially important societal role in advocating for change to address injustice and inequality. This was despite the majority having also been frustrated by the efficacy of their efforts, and the lack of action by state governance and public bodies. However, when constructed as only a product of exchange, this is a limited understanding of the responsibilities of academic knowledge production. The leap to outputs, recommendations and 'solutions', without deep theorisation or peer review, created conditions where many of such projects need not have been undertaken by academic citizens at all. In fact, many did not seek nor were situated within academic knowledge. The purpose in such cases seems to have been that the content was authorised by a figure of authority ('an academic') within an institution of legitimacy ('a university'). At the most extreme, such exchange becomes a spectacle (Debord, 1984) within a society that has commodified academic research.

Under half (49%) of the outputs were in the form of academic dissemination (papers, books, dissertations, conferences). A large amount of outputs were reports (26%), the remaining quarter were impact-related outputs. Only 23 of the 149 projects had more than one output. This may indicate that authors were not making, or were not capacitated to make, the most of their findings across audiences; or that the research may have been undertaken from extrinsic motivation, such as calls from funders or charities for an evidence-base on which to base their advocacy. 'Grant capture' has become a pressure within universities due to their under-funding within the UK and NI; and because they are run as businesses within the neoliberal order. Undertaking research for profit or private gain poses many risks to the role of the academic as critical consciousness in society, particularly when it becomes habitual or normalised, over research for truth or justice.

Few of the studies pointed to underpinning problematics in the knowledge generation, which is expected in research and particularly when about marginalised groups. Only 21% of the studies explicitly identified ethical clearance or conduct. Only some of these (what equated to 7% of the studies) discussed ethical matters in a more substantive way, such as about principles, dynamics, relations or quagmires negotiated during the research process. Less than 5% of the outputs referred to the researchers' positionality or insider-outsider status, which is unusual in an area enquiry where the politics of representation would have been foregrounded and when undertaking research about the context within which one is situated. This contrasted with the nature of the narrative reflections which authors shared in the interviews, many of which were highly self-critical. It may have been that the format, where they were assured their insights would not be linked to their public identities, allowed for such disclosure. Representations of research (such as in writing) are practices that fall within the protections of academic freedom, and thus ideally there should not be such self-censorship. The contrast suggests something of a fear or a strategic avoidance of public perception, to avoid the risk of weakening constructions of the researcher as providing 'objective knowledge' (Bastalich, 2023). For the area of enquiry, such risk avoidance may weaken future research as those coming in their

stead, will have less guidance to learn from. One of the newer researchers to this area highlighted the need for such peer knowledge, and a sense of the lack of access to such learning from what was available publicly.

Legitimacy has been a problematic area for NI research (Gilligan, 2022; D. C. Irwin, 2005; Knox, 2001; Taylor, 1988). It was the subject of a paper by Irwin (D. C. Irwin, 2005) writing about academic research on peace in NI. Within his careful crafting of principles for applied public opinion research in contexts of division and conflict, he draws on a solution proposed by Donald Campbell. That was, that the research process involves transparency ('full disclosure') and there is explicit inclusion and participation of adversarial stakeholders in the design process and in the interpretation of results. Such practices are not unusual in many research traditions, particularly contexts where public accountability and attempts to lessen hierarchical power dynamics are valued. However, such ethical practice is in sharp contrast to much of the outputs reviewed for this study, where so few included discussion (or even mention) of ethical considerations and of the researchers' positionality. The few that had information were declarative statements about ethical clearance, with only the exceptions sharing dilemmas, deliberations and their positionality. Yet this seemed the norm in the context, with this lack of transparency not undermining their legitimacy to undertake the work. During interviews with the participating authors, those not local shared some of the challenges in how their legitimacy was questioned. Some would use local colleagues, as last recourse when facing bureaucratic hurdles, such as when trying to get access to datasets or responses from public institutions. Less respect and more uncertainty was expressed when those academics sharing recommendations differed to the received local notion of the academic authority: those with accents, 'foreign sounding' surnames (i.e. not Anglophone or Western European), and those who were people racialised as other-than-'white'.

Such avoidance of complexity in relation to the construction of the academic researcher has been noted in prior studies of academic science in Northern Ireland (Taylor, 1988). In that study, it was interpreted as a response to establishing the legitimacy of the state and of the university in a context of tenuous legitimacy. While it is not widely acknowledged as such, the state of migrants and ethnic minorities (particularly those considered subordinate, including those racialised and those from eastern Europe), is a politically divisive topic in the country. Indications are that it is similarly the case for those racialised as other-than white within the universities, which would have been a double consciousness that academic authors racialised as other-than-'white' would need to negotiate. Thus, this study found that when it came to the study of migration and racialisation in this context, the politics of representation and authorship intersected in complex, and often adversely limiting ways, on academic autonomy. The implications of this for the university's role in democratising and deracialising the context is worrying.

REFERENCE LIST

- Bastalich, W. (2023). The devaluation of philosophical reflexivity in social research. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 0(0), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2023.2192464>
- BBC NI. (n.d.). *Equality Commission for Northern Ireland*. BBC NI. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/northernireland/schools/agreement/equality/equality1.s.html>
- Bell, M., & Lewis, N. (2022). Universities claim to value community-engaged scholarship: So why do they discourage it? *Public Understanding of Science, online first*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09636625221118779>
- Belluigi, D. Z., Macartney, M., Baysu, G., Burns, S., Butler, M., Crangle, J., Degenhardt, T., Devine, P., MacNamara, N., McLaughlin, K., McVeigh, R., Mikhael, D., Quinby, K., & Vieten, U. M. (2020). *Ethnic Disparities And Inequality In The UK: A Consultation Response From The RPA Consortium*. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/ethnic-disparities-and-inequality-in-the-uk-a-consultation-respon>
- Chan-Hu, E. (2023, August 6). Responses to draft about the context of Northern Ireland and ethnic minorities, Email correspondence with Dina Zoe Belluigi [Letter to Dina Zoe Belluigi].
- Crangle, J. (2018). 'Left to Fend for Themselves': Immigration, Race Relations and the State in Twentieth Century Northern Ireland. *Immigrants & Minorities*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619288.2018.1433534>
- Crangle, J. (2023). *Migrants, Immigration and Diversity in Twentieth-Century Northern Ireland*. Palgrave. <https://blackwells.co.uk/bookshop/product/Migrants-Immigration-and-Diversity-in-Twentieth-Century-Northern-Ireland-by-Jack-Crangle/9783031188206>
- Debord, G. (1984). *Society of the Spectacle*. Black & Red, U.S.
- ECNI. (n.d.). *Equality Commission for Northern Ireland*. <https://www.equalityni.org/Home>
- Gilligan, C. (2019). Northern Ireland and the limits of the race relations framework. *Capital & Class*, 43(1), 105–121. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309816818818090>
- Gilligan, C. (2022). Methodological nationalism and the Northern Ireland blind-spot in ethnic and racial studies. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 45(0), 431–451. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2021.1950793>
- GOV.UK. (2021). *Writing about ethnicity*. GOV.UK. <https://www.ethnicity-facts-figures.service.gov.uk/style-guide/writing-about-ethnicity>
- Hainsworth, P. (1998). *Divided society: Ethnic minorities and racism in Northern Ireland*. Pluto Press.
- Irwin, D. C. (2005). Public Opinion and the Politics of Peace Research: Northern Ireland, Balkans, Israel, Palestine, Cyprus, Muslim World and the 'War on Terror.' 34.
- Irwin, G., & Dunn, S. (1997). *Ethnic Minorities in Northern Ireland*. University of Ulster. <https://cain.ulster.ac.uk/csc/reports/ethnic.htm>
- Joynson, C., & Leyser, O. (2015). The culture of scientific research. *F1000Research*, 4, 66. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.6163.1>
- Knox, C. (2001). Establishing research legitimacy in the contested political ground of contemporary Northern Ireland. *Qualitative Research*, 1(2), 205–222. <https://doi.org/10.1177/146879410100100206>

- Kramer, A., Harvey, C., McEvoy, K., Bryson, A., O'Connell, R., Gormally, B., Holder, D., O'Hagan, F., Patterson-Bennett, E., & McKeown, G. (2018). *BrexitLawNI Policy Report: Brexit, Xenophobia and Racism in Northern Ireland*. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/brexitlawni-policy-report-brexit-xenophobia-and-racism-in-norther>
- Laux, R. (2019, March 7). *50 years of collecting ethnicity data—History of government*. GOV.UK. <https://history.blog.gov.uk/2019/03/07/50-years-of-collecting-ethnicity-data/>
- Lubit, A., & Belluigi, D. (2021). Collation and Mapping of Research related to Migrant and Minority Ethnic Matters in Northern Ireland produced within Northern Ireland's Universities:
- McAreavey, R. (2012). Resistance or Resilience? Tracking the Pathway of Recent Arrivals to a 'New' Rural Destination. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 52(4), 488–507. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9523.2012.00573.x>
- McGinnity, F., Laurence, J., & Cunniffe, E. (2023). *Comparing migrant integration in Ireland and Northern Ireland* (No. 158). Economic and Social Research Institute. <https://doi.org/10.26504/rs158>
- McVeigh, R., & Rolston, B. (2007). From Good Friday to Good Relations: Sectarianism, racism and the Northern Ireland state. *Race and Class*, 48(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306396807077009>
- Migrant and Minority Ethnic Thinktank. (2020, September 5). *'I Can't Breathe'—Statement by Migrant and Minority Ethnic Council of Northern Ireland*. Mme ThinkTank. <https://www.mmecouncil.org/post/i-can-t-breathe-statement-by-migrant-and-minority-ethnic-council-of-northern-ireland>
- Migrant and Minority Ethnic Thinktank. (2021, April 3). *Response to the Sewell Report*. Mme Council 3. <https://www.mmecouncil.org/post/response-to-the-sewell-report>
- Morier-Genoud, E. 2021. Diversity and race at QUB: A history of Africans and Africa since 1942. Paper presentation. Queen's University Belfast, 11 May.
- Moynihan, Y., & Belluigi, D. Z. (2022). Academic research outputs about local migrant and minority ethnic matters: Visualised findings from a systematic review of research produced in Northern Ireland (1994-2022). Queen's University Belfast. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/academic-research-outputs-about-local-migrant-and-minority-ethnic>
- MPs on the House of Commons Northern Ireland Affairs Committee. (2022). *Minority communities have often been overlooked in Northern Ireland*. House of Commons Committees. https://ukparliament.shorthandstories.com/minority-ethnic-and-migrant-people-experiences-NIAC-report/index.html?utm_source=committees.parliament.uk&utm_medium=referrals&utm_campaign=minority-ethnic-migrant-experiences-NI&utm_content=organic
- Murphy, F., & Vieten, U. M. (2017). Asylum seekers' and refugee's experiences of Life in Northern Ireland: Report of the first study on the situation of asylum seekers and refugees in NI. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/asylum-seekers-and-refugees-experiences-of-life-in-northern-irela>
- Murphy, F., & Vieten, U. M. (2022). Asylum seekers and refugees in Northern Ireland: The impact of post-migration stressors on mental health. *Irish Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 39(2), 163–172. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ipm.2020.102>
- NISRA. (2022a). *Main statistics for Northern Ireland Statistical bulletin Ethnicity*. Gov.uk. <https://www.nisra.gov.uk/system/files/statistics/census-2021-main-statistics-for-northern-ireland-phase-1-statistical-bulletin-ethnic-group.pdf>

- NISRA. (2022b). *Main statistics for Northern Ireland Statistical bulletin Language*.
<https://www.nisra.gov.uk/system/files/statistics/census-2021-main-statistics-for-northern-ireland-phase-1-press-release.pdf>
- NISRA. (2022c). *Main statistics for Northern Ireland statistical bulletin Religion*. NISRA.
<https://www.nisra.gov.uk/system/files/statistics/census-2021-main-statistics-for-northern-ireland-phase-1-statistical-bulletin-religion.pdf>
- NISRA. (2022d, September 7). *Census 2021 main statistics ethnicity tables*. Northern Ireland Statistics and Research Agency.
<https://www.nisra.gov.uk/publications/census-2021-main-statistics-ethnicity-tables>
- Northern Ireland Life & Times Survey. (2022). *Have you heard of the Racial Equality Strategy in NI?* (HRDRACEQ) [Data set]. ARK.
https://www.ark.ac.uk/nilt/2022/Minority_Ethnic_People/HRDRACEQ.html
- The Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order 1997, Pub. L. No. Schedule 2, N.I 6 869 (1997). <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/nisi/1997/869/schedule/2/made>
- Race Disparity Unit. (n.d.). *List of ethnic groups*. GOV.UK. <https://www.ethnicity-facts-figures.service.gov.uk/style-guide/ethnic-groups>
- Schubotz, D. (2005). Beyond the Orange and the Green. The Diversification of the Qualitative Social Research Landscape in Northern Ireland. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 6(3), Article 3.
<https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-6.3.11>
- Taylor, R. (1987). The limits of liberalism: The case of Queen's academics and the "Troubles." *Politics*, 7(2), 28–34.
- Taylor, R. (1988). Social Scientific Research on the "Troubles" in Northern Ireland: The Problem of Objectivity. *The Economic and Social Review*, 19(2), 123–145.
<http://hdl.handle.net/2262/68595>
- The Executive Office. (2005, July 1). *A Racial Equality Strategy for Northern Ireland 2005-2010*. The Executive Office. <https://www.executiveoffice-ni.gov.uk/publications/racial-equality-strategy-northern-ireland-2005-2010>
- The Executive Office. (2015, December 10). *Racial Equality Strategy 2015—2025*. The Executive Office. <https://www.executiveoffice-ni.gov.uk/publications/racial-equality-strategy-2015-2025>
- The Executive Office. (2022, February 21). *Refugee Integration Strategy for Northern Ireland 2022-2027 Consultation*. NI Direct.
<https://consultations.nidirect.gov.uk/teo/refugee-integration-strategy-for-northern-ireland/>
- Watson, A. M., & McKnight, E. (1998). Race and ethnicity in Northern Ireland: The Chinese Community. In P. Hainsworth (Ed.), *Divided Society: Ethnic Minorities and Racism in Northern Ireland*. Pluto Press.
<https://www.ark.ac.uk/orb/summaries/Wats98.htm>
- Zhang, L., & Sivertsen, G. (2021, November 15). Female researchers are more read and less cited because they more often engage in research for societal progress [LSE]. *Impact of Social Sciences*.
<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2021/11/15/female-researchers-are-more-read-and-less-cited-because-they-more-often-engage-in-research-for-societal-progress/>

APPENDICES

Appendix A Nomenclature

Decisions were made in this report, regarding the nomenclature related to 'race', 'ethnicity' and 'migration'. What was settled upon herein is in part informed by the intended readership, whom we anticipate will be mainly based within Northern Ireland, or the United Kingdom and the Republic of Ireland. We acknowledge that this is not consistent with international approaches, nor is it within the current recommended usages within academic literature. This section describes what informed our decisions, noting that there are differences between jurisdictions, histories, and the purpose of our research which, for instance, does not involve 'monitoring'.

The word 'race' is used within the various legislations to do with *discrimination* in the UK. Within NI, such legislation is the Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order (The Race Relations (Northern Ireland) Order 1997, 1997). Use of the term within this report is when the issues raised or findings described were related to race-based discrimination. Neither the report writers nor named organisations herein, ascribe to delusions that 'races' exist whatsoever, beyond their fabrication as social constructs which have had tangible impacts.

The use of the word 'ethnicity' is a recent addition to the nomenclature of UK governance and population monitoring. The distinction made between 'race' and 'ethnicity' in such discourse is that the former is to distinguish social groups "in terms of a person's skin colour, nationality, and ethnic or national origins" (Laux, 2019, p. n.p.). Within texts published on the platforms of the National Archive of Downing Street, the description of how 'ethnicity' differs is outlined below:

Ethnicity, however, is more subjective – it relates to a shared history and culture, language, religion and traditions, as well as skin colour.

The way that ethnic groups are defined has changed over time. Similarly, the way someone describes themselves may change as their perceptions, or society's, change. And, society's needs for information about ethnicity have changed over time.

This makes collecting ethnicity data, and measuring changes over time, challenging. (Laux, 2019, p. n.p.)

Explicit within the historical narrative of Census monitoring in Great Britain, was the desire to somehow distinguish those racialised as 'white' over those racialised as other-than-white, which was formalised with decolonisation in the 1960's to limit and monitor which of those of former colonies migrated to Great Britain. That was not a demarcation of socio-cultural identification (unlike the definition of self-reported ethnicity described above suggests). Rather it was informed by, and thus re-inscribed, categorisations of people and groups fabricated by erroneous pseudo-scientific

concoctions of racism of the day. This is revealed in comments within that narrative, such as that the 1960's distinctions between the 'Old', 'New', and 'African' Commonwealth made it "hard to see these groups as good indicators of ethnicity – for example, many people born in the New Commonwealth were White."

The shift towards ethnicity over racial categories has been a response to social movements' assertions of autonomy and self-identification, over state-imposed racialisation. Which social groups have been delineated within the terminology of 'ethnic minority' has changed over time, and differs in the devolved nations of the UK. For the 2021 Census in Northern Ireland, the screen capture below outlines the ethnic groupings utilised.

4. Scotland and Northern Ireland

The Censuses in Scotland and Northern Ireland use different ethnicity classifications.

Northern Ireland

The ethnicity question in the [2021 Census in Northern Ireland](#) asked people to choose from the following ethnic groups:

- Black African
- Black Other
- Chinese
- Filipino
- Indian
- Irish Traveller
- Mixed ethnic group
- Roma
- White
- Any other ethnic group

Figure 26 The classifications of ethnicity for the Census data of Northern Ireland which differs to other jurisdictions (Race Disparity Unit, n.d.)

A note added in a report analysing 'ethnicity' data of Census 2021 makes explicit how the term 'ethnic minority' is interpreted at the time of writing for population monitoring purposes.

In the following analysis the label 'minority ethnic group' is used. This relates to all persons who have an ethnicity classification other than the 'White' option... (NISRA, 2022a, p. 4)

This statement makes it clear that 'ethnic minority' stands as a proxy for the minority groups racialised as other-than-white. Irish Travellers and Roma are groups that are minorities within NI, fall into the definitions of 'ethnicity' described above, and indeed may or may not be classified as white. Thus, such data collection is inconsistent for monitoring over time and across the UK. Many of the groupings used for NI Census

data do not meet the definition of ethnicity about that which is 'shared'. For instance, 'Black African' would include those born within or descendent from any of the countries on the African continent, or from anywhere in the world, where histories, languages, cultures, and complexions differ. Importantly, it may not involve identifications of shared ethnicity by the person themselves, except in a context such as NI where such classifications are imposed. Other Africa-born groups with shared cultures, language et cetera are excluded from this group, where they are classified as 'Indian', 'white' or 'mixed'. In addition, grouping such as the Polish from Eastern Europe have socio-cultural connections that would fall under the general description of ethnicity provided above, and are a minority group. Within solidaristic civil society groups within NI, many of the groupings listed above would interact as 'ethnic minorities', including those Polish or of Polish descent in NI. However, because they are racialised as 'white' in NI, they are not classified as 'ethnic minorities' within the strict confines of current approach above in NI.

Political correctness may be obscuring acknowledgement that the current criteria for inclusion/ exclusion within the nomenclature of 'ethnic minority' is more accurately to distinguish 'racialised minorities' from the 'white' majority'. Racial monitoring is often justified as of importance for identifying and addressing inequalities. Whether that is indeed the way in which such data is utilised within NI, is not within the scope of this report. However, this study's intention was not to monitor nor re-inscribe racialisations. Rather, it was to look at how academic research approaches the study of 'ethnic minorities' and migrants in NI, inclusive of the treatment of the question of constructions, dis/advantage and discrimination related to race, but not exclusively about racialised minorities. It was also to consider inequalities within the politics of representation for authoring knowledge.

The term 'Black, Asian, minority ethnic' was adopted within the UK at a point in time to distinguish the racial category 'white' from those broadly falling within 'Black' (i.e. inclusive of all racialised within 'Black African descent'); from the various racialised groups that would fall under those descending or from the Asian continent, from those minorities which included those 'white' but were not majority ethnicities of Great Britain and Northern Ireland. The variations to the acronym have altered in response to pressures from social movements with race consciousness in the face of continued discriminations. However, the usage of these terms too has been recognised as problematic and insufficient. It both disallows more distinct and varied self-identification; and may obscure distinct and varied kinds of oppression.

A preference by the first author was to use the phrase 'person of colour'. However, feedback from non-academic readers based in NI indicated this may be misinterpreted because it is not in common use. When connected to the national identity of the primary investigator, it allowed for problematic associations with one of apartheid South Africa's racialised classifications.

We noted the variations in the nomenclature related to ethnicity/ race, in the research outputs we analysed within this report. The challenge came when the

authors of this report tried to describe intersecting identities, such as in the section of authorship. We decided to use 'ethnic minority' in the broadest sense, to indicate those not of the 'ethnic majority' in NI who are of either Protestant or Catholic religious background, speak English/ Irish/ Ulster-Scots, who are settled, and have been racialised as 'white'. 'Ethnic minority' in our approach included Travellers and Roma, and those descendent of various groups who could be racialised as 'white' but not of the 'ethnic majority'. However, where relevant we have also indicated where such 'ethnic minorities' were not racialised as white, to distinguish different kinds of dis/advantage or discrimination. This approach was somewhat consistent with the guidelines provided in the text 'Writing about ethnicity' (GOV.UK, 2021): It is an awkward and unsatisfactory solution, in that it continues to distinguish against whiteness.

For comparisons with the white group as a whole, we use 'all other ethnic groups combined' or 'ethnic minorities (excluding white minorities)'. We also refer to 'white' and 'other than white' if space is limited.

We did not use such wording when asking participants to self-identify. The phrases 'other-than-white' or 'not racialised as white' were used specifically when identifying racialised outcomes. This was particularly the case in the authorship of academic texts.

A note of the use of the word 'migrant'. The widest interpretation was used in this report, with the intention to include those whose migration (whether temporary or permanent) was to NI. This included 'internal migrants' such as those from other jurisdictions of the UK, which was a self-identification that a number of the authors raised because of their experiences of being 'othered' within NI culturally. It also includes those migrant from ROI, which is correct according to definition in the law, because anyone not born in NI (which is in law part of the UK) is legally defined as a migrant (McGinnity et al., 2023). We did not ascribe to differentiations nor negative stratifications between groups of people who are migrant, in the ways commonly politicised in discourses on the subject. Again, we showed within the report some of the varied associated terms with that nomenclature which appeared within the analysed research outputs; and the contrast between how the participating authors' self-identified and how they reported they were classified legally within the UK.

'Minority' indicates the relative size of the populations under study, compared to the majority group. Of importance to note is that many were not minoritized in terms of 'ethnicity' nor 'racialisation' within the countries or continents of origin.

Appendix B Research items per category

Prior to commencing this project, a scoping review was undertaken. It was supervised by Dr Belluigi with Dr Amanda Lubit as research assistant, in partnership with the MMETT and supported with funding by the Impact Acceleration Account of QUB. The MMETT determined the topic areas that would be most of interest to non-academic audience, informed by their expertise in the 'community sector' and civil rights sector.

The data visualization below, indicates the topics on which the outputs predominantly focused. Note that it was informed by the outputs produced up until early 2021 (Lubit and Belluigi, 2021)

Figure 27 Research items per primary subject category, with indications of more recent outputs

Of the items collated in the scoping review, forty-one percent (41%) had been produced in the period 2017-2021, though there was variation in which subjects were researched. This is indicated in Figure 27, which visualises all eight categories, indicating differences between the number of sources over the past five years with the number of sources over all time. Points noted included:

- **Criminal Justice** was one of the largest areas of research, both more recently and over time.
- **Education** was also an area with more research comparatively.
- **Employment** as a topic had significantly decreased over the time period.
- **Environment** was the least popular, yet half had been undertaken within the more recent timeframe.
- **Health** has significantly increased, with the majority being undertaken more recently.
- **Housing** had increased over time but had not seen many research projects.

- **Discrimination** was a cross-cutting category that incorporated research from the other categories (e.g. it includes discrimination in education, employment, health and housing). Nearly one-third of all research on discrimination was published in the more recent timeframe.
- **Legislation** was cross-cutting. It was comparatively moderately well-researched over all time.

Appendix C Output items of the SLR dataset

- Agarin, T. (2019) 'The Limits of Inclusion: Representation of Minority and Non-Dominant Communities in Consociational and Liberal Democracies: Representation of minority and non-dominant communities in consociational and liberal democracies', *International Political Science Review* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192512119881801>
- Agarin, T. and McCulloch, A. (2019) 'How power-sharing includes and excludes non-dominant communities: Introduction to the special issue', *International Political Science Review* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192512119873075>
- Agarin, T., McCulloch, A. and Murtagh, C. (2018) 'Others in deeply divided societies: A research agenda', *Nationalism and Ethnic Politics*, 24(3), pp. 299–310. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13537113.2018.1489488>
- Allamby, L. et al. (2011) 'Forced Labour in Northern Ireland: exploiting vulnerability'. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/forced-labour-in-northern-ireland-exploiting-vulnerability> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- ARK and Conflict Textiles (2021) *Refugees and asylum seekers in Northern Ireland*, ARK. Available at: <https://www.ark.ac.uk/Newsletters/ARK-Newsletter-6-2021.html#517> (Accessed: 29 June 2021).
- Baum, T., Hearn, N. and Devine, F. (2007) 'Place, people and interpretation: issues of migrant labour and tourism imagery in Ireland', *Tourism Recreation Research*, 32(3), pp. 39–48. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2007.11081538>
- Bellugi, D.Z. et al. (2020) *Ethnic Disparities And Inequality In The UK: A Consultation Response From The RPA Consortium*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/ethnic-disparities-and-inequality-in-the-uk-a-consultation-respon> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Bellugi, D.Z. and Joseph, E. (2021) 'Within the award funding gap: The Im-possibility of an All Ireland Africanist network in 2020', *African Identities* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14725843.2021.1986367>
- Biggart, A., O'Hare, L. and Connolly, P. (2008) A need to belong: An epidemiological study of black and minority ethnic children's perceptions of exclusion in the southern area of Northern Ireland. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/a-need-to-belong-an-epidemiological-study-of-black-and-minority-e> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Biggart, A., O'Hare, L. and Connolly, P. (2013) 'A need to belong?: The prevalence of experiences of belonging and exclusion in school among minority ethnic children living in the "White hinterlands"', *Irish Educational Studies*, 32(2), pp. 179–195. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2013.765264>
- Bloomer, F., Hamilton, J. and Potter, M. (2014) 'Challenges and barriers in primary school education: The experiences of Traveller children and young people in Northern Ireland', *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*, 9(1), pp. 3–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1746197913475767>
- Bloomer, S. (2019) 'Assessing the Impact of Labour Market Integration Strategies through the Lens of Migrant Worker Experiences in the Mushroom Industry', in. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/assessing-the-impact-of-labour-market-integration-strategies-thro> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Bloomsbury Collections - *Enforcing Silence - Academic Freedom, Palestine and the Criticism of Israel* (no date). Available at: <https://www.bloomsburycollections.com/book/enforcing-silence-academic-freedom-palestine-and-the-criticism-of-israel/about-the-contributors?from=search> (Accessed: 8 April 2021).
- Bosqui, T. et al. (2019) 'First-generation migrants' use of psychotropic medication in Northern Ireland a record linkage study', *International journal of mental health systems*, 13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13033-019-0334-3>
- BrexitLawNI et al. (2018) *Brexit, Border Controls and Free Movement*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/brexit-border-controls-and-free-movement> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Building Resilience Across Borders* (no date). Available at: <https://publicservices.international/resources/publications/building-resilience-across-borders?id=11444&lang=en> (Accessed: 8 March 2021).

- Burns, S., Lyons, E. and Niens, U. (2016) "'The world would just fall apart if there's no respect at all': Children's understandings of respect for diversity in a post-conflict society', *Journal of Peace Education* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17400201.2016.1269313>
- Button, D. et al. (2020) *Patients Not Passports: Learning from the international struggle for universal healthcare*. London: New Economics Foundation. Available at: https://neweconomics.org/uploads/files/NEF_Patients-not-passports.pdf (Accessed: 8 March 2021).
- Byrne, J. and Hamilton, J. (2005) New migrant communities in East Tyrone: a review of the attitudes of staff and students at East Tyrone College towards the migrant population. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/new-migrant-communities-in-east-tyrone-a-review-of-the-attitudes--2> (Accessed: 10 March 2021).
- Byrne, J. and Hamilton, J. (2007) Rhythms and Realities of Everyday Life: A study of the impact of new migrant in Dungannon, part of a wider UK-wide research project. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/rhythms-and-realities-of-everyday-life-a-study-of-the-impact-of-n-2> (Accessed: 10 March 2021).
- Carruthers, J. and Mainnin, M.O. (2017) 'Languages in Northern Ireland: Policy and Practice', in *Languages After Brexit. How the UK Speaks to the World*, pp. 159–172. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/languages-in-northern-ireland-policy-and-practice> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Carruthers, J. and Nandi, A. (2020) 'Supporting Speakers of Community Languages. A Case Study of Policy and Practice in Primary Schools', *Current Issues in Language Planning* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14664208.2020.1838748>
- Cena, E., Burns, S. and Wilson, P. (2021) 'Sense of belonging, intercultural and academic experiences among international students at a University in Northern Ireland', *Journal of International Students*, 11(4), pp. 812–831. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.32674/jis.v11i4.2541>
- Chan, S. (2006) "'God's Little Acre", "Belfast Chinatown": diversity and ethnic place identity in Belfast', in *Unknown Host Publication*. FEEM Working Papers, Social Science Research Network. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/gods-little-acre-belfast-chinatown-diversity-and-ethnic-place-ide-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Close, C. et al. (2017) 'Migrant mental health and representation in routine administrative registers', *International Journal of Migration, Health and Social Care*, 14(1), pp. 1–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMHS-09-2016-0035>
- Clough, G. and Adams, A. (2020) 'Evidence Cafes: Overcoming conflicting motivations and timings', *Research for All*, 4(2), pp. 145–149 <http://oro.open.ac.uk/71172/>
- Connolly, P. (2002) *'Race' and Racism in Northern Ireland: A Review of the Research Evidence*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/race-and-racism-in-northern-ireland-a-review-of-the-research-evid> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Connolly, P. (2006) 'It goes without saying (well, sometimes): racism, whiteness and identity in Northern Ireland', in *The New Countryside? Ethnicity, Nation and Exclusion in Contemporary Rural Britain*, pp. 21–46. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/it-goes-without-saying-well-sometimes-racism-whiteness-and-identi> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Connolly, P. and Keenan, M. (1999) *The employment and training needs of minority ethnic people in Northern Ireland*, pp. 47–58. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/the-employment-and-training-needs-of-minority-ethnic-people-in-no> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Connolly, P. and Keenan, M. (2000) *Opportunities for All: Minority Ethnic People's Experiences of Education, Training and Employment in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/opportunities-for-all-minority-ethnic-peoples-experiences-of-educ> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Connolly, P. and Keenan, M. (2002) 'Racist harassment in the white hinterlands: minority ethnic children and parents' experiences in schools in Northern Ireland', pp. 341–356. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/racist-harassment-in-the-white-hinterlands-minority-ethnic-childr>
- Connolly, P. and Khaoury, R. (2010) 'Whiteness, racism and exclusion in Northern Ireland: A critical race perspective', *Northern Ireland after the Troubles? A Society in Transition*

- [Preprint]. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/whiteness-racism-and-exclusion-in-northern-ireland-a-critical-rac-2> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Craig, S. (2018) 'Implications of Brexit on Asylum in Northern Ireland', 11 May. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/implications-of-brexit-on-asylum-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Craith, M.N. and McMullan, A. (2006) 'A Spatial Analysis of In-Migration: A Case-Study of Northern Ireland', in *Negotiating Culture. Moving, Mixing and Memory in Contemporary Europe*, pp. 121–142. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/a-spatial-analysis-of-in-migration-a-case-study-of-northern-irela-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Craith, M.N., Odhiambo, E. and Moyo, K. (2008) *Giving Voice to Africans in Northern Ireland, West of the Bann*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/giving-voice-to-africans-in-northern-ireland-west-of-the-bann-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Crangle, J. (2018) "'Left to Fend for Themselves": Immigration, Race Relations and the State in Twentieth Century Northern Ireland', *Immigrants and Minorities*, 36(1), pp. 20–44. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619288.2018.1433534>
- Crooke, E. (2022) 'John Hewitt's "mental blush": Race and racism in the Belfast Museum: Ireland, Museums, Empire, Colonialism', in. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/john-hewitts-mental-blush-race-and-racism-in-the-belfast-museum-m> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).
- Cush, P. et al. (2020) 'Positive health among older Traveller and older homeless adults: a scoping review of life-course and structural determinants', *Health and Social Care in the Community*, pp. 1961–1978. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/hsc.13060>
- Devine, F. et al. (2006) 'Managing Cultural Diversity in Peripheral Tourism Destinations: Northern Ireland Experiences', in *Unknown Host Publication*. British Academy of Management. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/managing-cultural-diversity-in-peripheral-tourism-destinations-no-5> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Devine, F. et al. (2007a) 'Cultural Diversity in Hospitality Work: the Northern Ireland Experience', *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 18(2), pp. 333–349. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190601102596>
- Devine, F. et al. (2007b) 'Managing Cultural Diversity in Peripheral Tourism Destinations: Northern Ireland Experiences', *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 19(2), pp. 120–132. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596110710729238>
- Devine, F., Devine, A. and Elliott, G. (2016) 'Exploring the perceptions and attitudes of students on being prepared for the multicultural workplace', in *Unknown Host Publication*. Council for Hospitality Management Education. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/exploring-the-perceptions-and-attitudes-of-students-on-being-prep-3> (Accessed: 10 March 2021).
- Devine, P. (2018) 'Attitudes to minority ethnic groups in Northern Ireland, 2005-2016'. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/attitudes-to-minority-ethnic-groups-in-northern-ireland-2005-2016> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Donnan, H. (1998) "'Because you stick out, you stand out": perceptions of prejudice among Northern Ireland Pakistanis', in *Divided Society: Ethnic Minorities and Racism in Northern Ireland*, pp. 197–221. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/because-you-stick-out-you-stand-out-perceptions-of-prejudice-amon> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Doyle, C. and McAreavey, R. (2014) 'Possibilities for change? Diversity in Post-Conflict Belfast', *City: analysis of urban trends, culture, theory, policy, action*, 18(4–5), pp. 466–475. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13604813.2014.939467>
- Driver, C. (2009) 'The Question of "Good Relations" in Contested Spaces: Ethnic diversity and the role of representation in urban environments and the limitations of government support for the "good relations" strategy in Northern Ireland.', in *Unknown Host Publication*. Bauhaus-Universität Weimar. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/the-question-of-good-relations-in-contested-spaces-ethnic-diversi-2> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Durrer, V. and Henze, R. (eds) (2018) 'Cultural Inequalities', *Arts Management Quarterly* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://www.artsmangement.net/Journal/No-129-Cultural-Inequalities,144> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).

- Eaton, M. (2007) 'From Porto to Portadown: Portuguese workers in Northern Ireland's labour market', *Portuguese Journal of Social Science*, 6(3), pp. 171–191. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233600882_From_Porto_to_Portadown_Portuguese_workers_in_Northern_Ireland's_labour_market
- Eaton, M. (2010) 'Portuguese Migrant Worker Experiences in Northern Ireland's Market Town Economy', *Portuguese Studies*, 26(1), pp. 10–26. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/portuguese-migrant-worker-experiences-in-northern-irelands-market-3>
- Ellison, G. (2002) 'Sending out a message: Hate Crime in Northern Ireland', *Criminal Justice Matters*, 18(Summer), pp. 10–12. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/sending-out-a-message-hate-crime-in-northern-ireland>
- Ellison, G. (2013) 'The sex trade in Northern Ireland: the creation of a moral panic?', 27 September. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/the-sex-trade-in-northern-ireland-the-creation-of-a-moral-panic/> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Ellison, G. (2014) Written Evidence to NI Committee for Justice in respect of The Human Trafficking and Exploitation (Further Provisions and Support for Victims) Bill. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/written-evidence-to-ni-committee-for-justice-in-respect-of-the-hu> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Ellison, G. (2017) 'Criminalising the payment for sex in northern ireland; sketching the contours of a moral panic', *British Journal of Criminology*, 57(1), pp. 194–214. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azv107>
- Eyben, K., Morrow, D. and Wilson, D. (1997) *A Worthwhile Venture? Practically Investigating in Equity, Diversity and Interdependence in Northern Ireland*. Ulster University. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/a-worthwhile-venture-practically-investigating-in-equity-diversit-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Fanning, B. and Michael, L. (2017) 'Racism and anti-racism in the two Irelands', *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2017.1403641>
- Fitzgerald, L. et al. (2020) 'Human rights and theatre practice in Northern Ireland: A round-table discussion', *New Theatre Quarterly*, 36(4), pp. 279–291. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0266464X20000664>
- Fitzpatrick, C., Simpson, M. and McKeever, G. (2020) *Universal Credit: the wait for a first payment*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/universal-credit-the-wait-for-a-first-payment> (Accessed: 11 March 2021).
- Flanagan, D. and O'Boyle, A. (2021) 'Evaluation of a bespoke work-related English language course for newcomers in Northern Ireland', *Professional and Academic English*, 28(2), p. 71. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/evaluation-of-a-bespoke-work-related-english-language-course-for->
- Franklin, M. (2014) *Concepts of displacement and home: seeking asylum and becoming a refugee among the host community of Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/concepts-of-displacement-and-home-seeking-asylum-and-becoming-a-r> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Friel, B. and McDermott, P. (2018) *Shared Stories, Safe Spaces*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/shared-stories-safe-spaces> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Friel, B. and McDermott, P. (2019) *Youth Work in Diverse Societies: introduction*. Available at: <http://www.youthworkandyou.org> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).
- Glen, C., Taylor, L. and Dautel, J. (2019) 'Promoting prosocial behaviour toward refugees: Exploring the empathy-attitude-action model in middle childhood', in *Children and Peace: From Research to Action*, pp. 71–87. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/promoting-prosocial-behaviour-toward-refugees-exploring-the-empat> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Gray, A.M. and Horgan, G. (2009) *Figuring it Out: Looking behind the Social Statistics in Northern Ireland*. Access Research Knowledge. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/figuring-it-out-looking-behind-the-social-statistics-in-northern--3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).

- Gray, P., Long, G. and McAnulty, U. (2009) *Outlining Minimum Standards for Traveller Accommodation*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/outlining-minimum-standards-for-traveller-accommodation-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Hainsworth, P. (1996) 'Racism, Anti-Racism and the Extreme Right: the Republic of Ireland and Northern Ireland', *Newsletter: Contemporary European Studies Association of Australia*, December, pp. 4–9. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/racism-anti-racism-and-the-extreme-right-the-republic-of-ireland--3>
- Hainsworth, P. (1998a) *Divided Society Ethnic Minorities and Racism in Northern Ireland*. Pluto Press. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/divided-society-ethnic-minorities-and-racism-in-northern-ireland-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Hainsworth, P. (1998b) 'Introduction: Ethnic Minorities and Racism in a Divided Society', in *Divided Society: Ethnic Minorities and Racism in Northern Ireland*, pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/introduction-ethnic-minorities-and-racism-in-a-divided-society-6> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Hainsworth, P. (1998c) 'Politics, Racism and Ethnicity in Northern Ireland', in *Divided Society: Ethnic Minorities and Racism in Northern Ireland*, pp. 33–51. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/politics-racism-and-ethnicity-in-northern-ireland-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Hainsworth, P., Gilligan, C. and McGarry, A. (2008a) *Elected Representatives/ Political Parties and Minority Ethnic Communities in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/elected-representatives-political-parties-and-minority-ethnic-com-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Hainsworth, P., Gilligan, C. and McGarry, A. (2008) 'Political Parties and Minority Ethnic Communities in Northern Ireland: Election Manifestos 1994-2007', *Translocations: Migration and Social Change*, 3(1), pp. 1–28. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/politics-racism-and-ethnicity-in-northern-ireland-3>
- Hainsworth, P., Gilligan, C. and McGarry, A. (2008b) 'Questions and Answers: comparing the attitudes of elected representatives, political parties and the general public towards minority ethnic communities in Northern Ireland', *Shared Space*, 6, pp. 85–100. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/questions-and-answers-comparing-the-attitudes-of-elected-represen-3>
- Hainsworth, P., Gilligan, C. and McGarry, A. (2009) 'Accommodating Diversity in Northern Ireland: Elected Representatives and Minority Ethnic Communities', in *The Challenges of Peace: Research as a Contribution to Peace-Building in Northern Ireland*, pp. 207–222. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/accommodating-diversity-in-northern-ireland-elected-representativ-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Hamilton, J. et al. (2007) *Adequacy and Effectiveness of Educational Provision for Traveller Children and Young People in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/adequacy-and-effectiveness-of-educational-provision-for-traveller-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Hargie, O., Somerville, I. and Mitchell, D. (2015) *Social Exclusion and Sport in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/social-exclusion-and-sport-in-northern-ireland-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Hassan, D. (2013) 'Introduction', in *Ethnicity and Race in Association Football*. London: Routledge, pp. 1–5.
- Hassan, D. and McCue, K. (2013) 'The "silent" Irish – football, migrants and the pursuit of integration,' *Soccer and Society*, 14, pp. 1–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14660970.2013.801269>
- Hayward, K. and McManus, C. (2019) 'Northern Ireland: Society and Culture', in *The Routledge Handbook of British Politics and Society*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/northern-ireland-society-and-culture> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Hopkins, S. et al. (2021) *Draft Modern Slavery Strategy 2021-22. Response to the Department of Justice public consultation*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/draft-modern-slavery-strategy-2021-22-response-to-the-department-> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).

- Idowu-Eberendu, I.F. (2014) *Childhood and asylum : the legal protection of unaccompanied asylum seeking children and young people in the United Kingdom asylum and social care systems* / Ibidunni Francisca Idowu-Eberendu. Queen's University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/childhood-and-asylum-the-legal-protection-of-unaccompanied-asylum> (Accessed: 22 February 2021).
- 'Indian Migrants in Northern Ireland' (1990). Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/indian-migrants-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Jarman, N. (2012) *Criminal Justice Responses to Hate Crime in Northern Ireland*. HCINN. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/criminal-justice-responses-to-hate-crime-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Kane, F. et al. (2019) 'Language Made Fun: Supporting EAL students in primary education: Research into Early Years Language Learning', *Teanga*, 10, pp. 113–125. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.35903/teanga.v10i0.73>
- Karim, N. (2021) *Middle Eastern voluntary immigrant parents' experiences of child healthcare services in Northern Ireland*. Queens University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/middle-eastern-voluntary-immigrant-parents-experiences-of-child-h> (Accessed: 18 June 2022).
- Kelly, G. (2012) *Progressing Good Relations and Reconciliation in Post-Agreement Northern Ireland — Ulster University*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/progressing-good-relations-and-reconciliation-in-post-agreement-n-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Kelly, G. (2018) *In their own words: Young People's Attitudes to Community Relations in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/in-their-own-words-young-peoples-attitudes-to-community-relations> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Kempny, M. (2010) *Crossing boundaries of cultures and identities: Polish migrants in Belfast*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/crossing-boundaries-of-cultures-and-identities-polish-migrants-in> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Khan, N. (2020) *Cross-cultural Research on the Predictors of Young Women's Same-Sex Friendship Quality in the Context of Muslims in the UK and Pakistan*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/cross-cultural-research-on-the-predictors-of-young-womens-same-se> (Accessed: 22 February 2021).
- Khaoury, R. (2012) *The schooling experiences of minority ethnic students in Northern Ireland*. Queen's University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/the-schooling-experiences-of-minority-ethnic-students-in-northern> (Accessed: 22 February 2021).
- Knox, C. (2011) 'Tackling Racism in Northern Ireland: "The Race Hate Capital of Europe"', *Journal of Social Policy*, 40(2), pp. 387–412. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/tackling-racism-in-northern-ireland-the-race-hate-capital-of-euro-3>
- Knox, C. and Jarman, N. (2005) *The Challenge of Diversity: Hate Crime in Northern Ireland: Volume II*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/the-challenge-of-diversity-hate-crime-in-northern-ireland-volume--6> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Kramer, A. et al. (2018) *BrexitLawNI Policy Report: Brexit, Xenophobia and Racism in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/brexitlawni-policy-report-brexit-xenophobia-and-racism-in-norther> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Linse, C. (2016) 'Formal and informal translation and interpretation for immigrants and asylum seekers'. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/formal-and-informal-translation-and-interpretation-for-immigrants> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Lippard, C.D. and McNamee, C.B. (2021) 'Are refugees really welcome? Understanding Northern Ireland attitudes towards Syrian refugees', *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 34(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jrs/feab030>
- 'Lockdown routines: Im/mobility, materiality and mediated support at the time of the pandemic' (2022) in *Material Culture and (Forced) Migration*. London: UCL Press. Available at: <https://www.uclpress.co.uk/products/182510> (Accessed: 21 February 2022).
- Lubit, A. (2020) 'Digital Connectivity: Something we take for granted', *A Changing World: Reflections from the HAPP community and beyond*, 20 May. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/digital-connectivity-something-we-take-for-granted> (Accessed: 25 February 2021).

- Lubit, A.J. (2022) 'A Mother's Experience of Asylum: Conflicting Temporalities, Belonging, and Evolving Care Relations', *Journal of Intercultural Studies*, 43(4), pp. 464–479. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07256868.2022.2086226>
- Mackle, D. et al. (2018) *FGM Scoping Study Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/fgm-scoping-study-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- MacNamara, N. et al. (2020) 'Interrogating the politicization of female genital cutting (FGC) within conditions of asymmetrical cultural convergence. A case study of Northern Ireland.', *Women's Studies International Forum*, 82, p. 102391. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2020.102391>
- Maginn, P. and Ellison, G. (2014) 'Male Sex Work in the Irish Republic and Northern Ireland', in *Male Sex Work and Society*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/male-sex-work-in-the-irish-republic-and-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Mahadeo, M. (2012) 'Globalisation, Migration and Interculturalism; the role of community activism', *The Irish Journal of Community Work*, 3, pp. 124–138.
- Marginal Players? The Third Sector and Employability Services for Migrants, Refugees and Asylum Seekers in the UK | SpringerLink (no date). Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11266-020-00306-6> (Accessed: 8 March 2021).
- Marshall, T. (2018) "'There is no Hindu community in Northern Ireland": Diasporic Place-Making amongst Belfast's Hindus - Research in Religion Conference, The University of Edinburgh', in. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/there-is-no-hindu-community-in-northern-ireland-diasporic-place-m>
- Marshall, T. (2020) 'Soda Bread and Herrings: Are Intercultural Events Truly Intercultural? Sensing Divisions Conference, Queen's University, Belfast', in. Queens University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/soda-bread-and-herrings-are-intercultural-events-truly-intercultu>
- Marshall, T. (2021) 'Śledzie and Soda Bread: Are Intercultural Events Truly Intercultural?', *Irish Journal of Arts Management and Cultural Policy*, 8, pp. 29–53. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/%C5%9Bledzie-and-soda-bread-are-intercultural-events-truly-intercultu>
- McAreavey, R. (2010a) 'Life as a Stranger' - *The personal stories of migrants to Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/life-as-a-stranger-the-personal-stories-of-migrants-to-northern-i> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- McAreavey, R. (2010b) 'Transcending cultural differences: the role of language in migrants' integration', *Translocations: Migration and Social Change*, 6(2). Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/transcending-cultural-differences-the-role-of-language-in-migrant> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- McAreavey, R. (2012) 'Resistance or Resilience? Tracking the Pathway of Recent Arrivals to a "New" Rural Destination', *Sociologia Ruralis*, 52(4), pp. 488–507. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9523.2012.00573.x>
- McAreavey, R. (2013) 'Migration to Northern Ireland', 1 July. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/migration-to-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- McAreavey, R. (2014a) 'Doing Focus Groups and Interviews with Recent Migrants to Northern Ireland: A Dynamic Interplay of Ethics, Language and Access'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/978144627305014533917>
- McAreavey, R. (2014b) 'Poverty, ethnicity and international migrants to Northern Ireland: New opportunities or new vulnerabilities?' Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/poverty-ethnicity-and-international-migrants-to-northern-ireland-> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- McAreavey, R. (2015a) 'Minority and majority community integration in Northern Ireland: a matrix of tolerance', in *Tolerance and Diversity in Ireland – North and South*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/minority-and-majority-community-integration-in-northern-ireland-a> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- McAreavey, R. (2015b) 'Recent migrants to Northern Ireland: understanding new configurations of "community"', in *A Sense of Place: Multidisciplinary Essays in Honour of Malachy*

- McEldowney. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/recent-migrants-to-northern-ireland-understanding-new-configurati> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- McAreavey, R. (2017) 'Migrant identities in a new immigrant destination: revealing the limitations of the "hard working" migrant identity', *Population, Space and Place* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2044>
- McAreavey, R. and Das, C. (2013) 'A Delicate Balancing Act: Negotiating with Gatekeepers for Ethical Research When Researching Minority Communities', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 12(1), pp. 113–131.
- McAreavey, R., Irwin, J. and Murphy, N. (2014) *The Social and Economic Mobility of Ethnic Minority Communities in Northern Ireland*. Joseph Rowntree Foundation. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/the-social-and-economic-mobility-of-ethnic-minority-communities-i> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- McCartan, C. (2019) *Power, inequality and social justice*. Queen's University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/power-inequality-and-social-justice> (Accessed: 22 February 2021).
- McDermott, P. (2008a) 'Acquisition, Loss or Multilingualism? Educational Planning for Speakers of Migrant Community Languages in Northern Ireland', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 9(4), pp. 483–500. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/acquisition-loss-or-multilingualism-educational-planning-for-spea-3>
- McDermott, P. (2008b) 'Towards Linguistic Diversity? Community Languages in Northern Ireland', *Shared Space: A research journal on peace, conflict and community relations in Northern Ireland*, 5, pp. 5–20. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/towards-linguistic-diversity-community-languages-in-northern-irel-3>
- McDermott, P. (2011) *Migrant Languages in the Public Space: A Case Study from Northern Ireland*. LIT Verlag. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/migrant-languages-in-the-public-space-a-case-study-from-northern--3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- McDermott, P. (2012) 'Cohesion, sharing and integration? Migrant languages and cultural spaces in Northern Ireland's urban environment', *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 13(3), pp. 187–205. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14664208.2012.722377>
- McDermott, P. (2013) A 'Shared Society'? *Attitudes on immigration and diversity (Research Update 86)*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/a-shared-society-attitudes-on-immigration-and-diversity-research--3> (Accessed: 10 March 2021).
- McDermott, P. (2014) *Research Update 95: Intolerance towards minority ethnic communities: An overview of responses 2005-2013*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/research-update-95-intolerance-towards-minority-ethnic-communitie-3> (Accessed: 10 March 2021).
- McDermott, P. (2015) *Attitudes towards minority ethnic people and migrant workers 2014*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/attitudes-towards-minority-ethnic-people-and-migrant-workers-2014-3> (Accessed: 10 March 2021).
- McDermott, P. (2016) 'Immigration, Race and Ethnicity in an Already Divided Society', in *Politics of Identity in Post-Conflict States: The Bosnian and Irish Experience*, pp. 207–222. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/immigration-race-and-ethnicity-in-an-already-divided-society-3> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- McDermott, P. and Odhiambo, E. (2010) 'Negotiating Belonging: Discourse on Culture and Language for Migrants from the Global South', *Policy and Practice: A Development Education Review*, 11, pp. 112–119. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/negotiating-belonging-discourse-on-culture-and-language-for-migra-3>
- McKeever, E. (2017) *The construction of collective identity in Northern Ireland in relation to minority ethnic and immigrant populations*. Queens University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/the-construction-of-collective-identity-in-northern-ireland-in-re> (Accessed: 18 June 2022).
- McKeever, G., Simpson, M. and Fitzpatrick, C. (2018) *Destitution and paths to justice*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/destitution-and-paths-to-justice> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- McKendrick, J.H. et al. (2008) 'The Media, Poverty and Public Opinion in the UK' (2008). (Joseph Rowntree funded co-authored report on media coverage and audience understanding of

- issues of poverty in the UK). Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/the-media-poverty-and-public-opinion-in-the-uk-2008-joseph-rowntree-2> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- McManus, C. (2010) 'Understanding Racial Tensions in Northern Ireland: Threat, Paranoia and the Fear of Loss', *International Journal of Diversity in Organizations, Communities and Nations*, 10(4), pp. 217–226. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/understanding-racial-tensions-in-northern-ireland-threat-paranoia>
- McMonagle, S. and McDermott, P. (2014) 'Transitional Politics and Language Rights in a Multi-ethnic Northern Ireland: Towards a True Linguistic Pluralism?', *Ethnopolitics*, 13(3), pp. 245–266. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17449057.2013.858935>
- McNaull, G. et al. (no date) 'Sex Work and Criminalisation'. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/sex-work-and-criminalisation> (Accessed: 3 February 2021). <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/sex-work-and-criminalisation>
- McPhillips, K. and Russell, J. (2011) 'The Relationship between Youth Identity and Spatial Perception within the Context of Religious Architecture in Northern Ireland.', *International Journal of the Constructed Environment*, 1, pp. 97–114. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/the-relationship-between-youth-identity-and-spatial-perception-wi-3>
- McVeigh, R. and Rolston, B. (2007) 'From Good Friday to Good Relations: sectarianism, racism and the Northern Ireland state', *Race and Class*, 48(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306396807077009>
- McWilliams, M. and Yarnell, P. (2013) *The Protection and Rights of Black and Minority Ethnic Women Experiencing Domestic Violence in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/the-protection-and-rights-of-black-and-minority-ethnic-women-expe-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- McWilliams, M., Yarnell, P. and Churchill, M. (2016) 'Forced Dependency and Legal Barriers: Implications of the UK's Immigration and Social Security Policies for Minoritized Women Living in Abusive Intimate Relationships in Northern Ireland', *Oñati Socio-legal Series*, 5(6), pp. 1536–1556. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/forced-dependency-and-legal-barriers-implications-of-the-uks-immi>
- Michael, L. (2015) *Afrophobia in Ireland: Racism against People of African Descent*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/afrophobia-in-ireland-racism-against-people-of-african-descent-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Michael, L. (2016) *Race Equality Works for Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/race-equality-works-for-northern-ireland-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Michael, L. (2017) *Racism and intolerance towards minority ethnic groups in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/racism-and-intolerance-towards-minority-ethnic-groups-in-northern> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Michael, L. and Devine, P. (2018) *A welcoming Northern Ireland? Understanding sentiment towards asylum seekers and refugees*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/a-welcoming-northern-ireland-understanding-sentiment-towards-asyl> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Morrison, A. et al. (2018) *Anti-poverty practice framework for social work in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/anti-poverty-practice-framework-for-social-work-in-northern-irela> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Mulholland, C. (2016) *Making Space for Each Other: Civic Place-Making in a Divided Society*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/making-space-for-each-other-civic-place-making-in-a-divided-socie> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Murphy, A. (2015) *Migration to new destinations: Local migrant experiences in a globalised world*. Queen's University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/migration-to-new-destinations-local-migrant-experiences-in-a-glob> (Accessed: 22 February 2021).
- Murphy, F. (2018) 'Seeking Refuge in Northern Ireland'. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/seeking-refuge-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).

- Murphy, F. and Vieten, U.M. (2017a) 'Asylum seekers' and refugee's experiences of Life in Northern Ireland: Report of the first study on the situation of asylum seekers and refugees in NI - 2016. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/asylum-seekers-and-refugees-experiences-of-life-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Murphy, F. and Vieten, U.M. (2017b) *Asylum seekers and refugees in Northern Ireland: A policy brief*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/asylum-seekers-and-refugees-in-northern-ireland-a-policy-brief> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Murphy, F. and Vieten, U.M. (2017c) 'What life is like for asylum seekers and refugees in Northern Ireland'. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/what-life-is-like-for-asylum-seekers-and-refugees-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Murphy, F. and Vieten, U.M. (2019) 'African asylum seekers and refugees in both Irelands', in *Immigrants as outsiders in the two Irelands*, pp. 58–71. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/african-asylum-seekers-and-refugees-in-both-irelands> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Murphy, F. and Vieten, U.M. (2020) 'Asylum Seekers and Refugees in Northern Ireland: The impact of postmigration stressors on mental health', *Irish Journal of Psychological Medicine* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/ipm.2020.102>
- Nagle, J. (2014) "'Nightmare in Northern Ireland seeing race replace religion as society's open sore'", 6 June. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/nightmare-in-northern-ireland-seeing-race-replace-religion-as-society> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Nicholl, P. et al. (2016) 'An Evaluation of Social Work Practice in the Northern Ireland Guardian Ad Litem Agency in Working with Children and Families from Black Minority Ethnic Communities', *Child Care in Practice*, 22(4), pp. 335–347. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13575279.2016.1188762>
- Niens, U., Reilly, J. and McEvoy, R. (2005) 'Education for a Bill of Rights for Northern Ireland.', in *Teachers, Human Rights and Diversity: educating citizens in multicultural societies*, pp. 53–72. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/education-for-a-bill-of-rights-for-northern-ireland-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- 'Northern Ireland Assembly Official Report (Hansard): Human Trafficking and Exploitation (Further Provisions and Support for Victims) Bill, Oral Evidence to Committee' (2014). Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/northern-ireland-assembly-official-report-hansard-human-trafficking> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Odhiambo, E. and McDermott, P. (2010) *Voices From the Global South*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/voices-from-the-global-south-3> (Accessed: 10 March 2021).
- O'Neill, S. and O'Connor, R. (2020) 'Suicide in Northern Ireland: epidemiology, risk factors, and prevention', *Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(6), pp. 538–546. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(19\)30525-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(19)30525-5)
- O'Reilly, D. and Stevenson, M. (2003) 'Selective migration from deprived areas in Northern Ireland and the spatial distribution of inequalities: implications for monitoring health and inequalities in health', *Social Science and Medicine*, 57(8)(8), pp. 1455–1462. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(02\)00540-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(02)00540-3)
- Orlik, W. and Shevlin, M. (2016) 'Psychological Status and Well-Being of a large Sample of Polish Migrants in Ireland', *Irish journal of Psychology*, n/a. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03033910.2016.1194771>
- 'Other Faces: Indians in Northern Ireland' (1991). Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/other-faces-indians-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- OURSELVES ALONE: *The Prehistory of the Crisis (II)* (2009). Available at: <http://www.susannebosch.de/33.0.html> (Accessed: 29 June 2022).
- Patel, K. (2020) *The Usefulness of Administrative Data in the Research of Migrant Health*. Queen's University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/the-usefulness-of-administrative-data-in-the-research-of-migrant-health> (Accessed: 22 February 2021).
- Patel, K. et al. (2021) 'Unmet need for mental health medication within the migrant population of Northern Ireland: a record linkage study', *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 75(3), pp. 245–250. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2019-212774>

- Patrick, R. and Simpson, M. (2020) *Universal Credit could be a lifeline in Northern Ireland, but it must be designed with people who use it*. Joseph Rowntree Foundation. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/universal-credit-could-be-a-lifeline-in-northern-ireland-but-it-m> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Pehrson, S., Gheorghiu, M. and Ireland, T. (2012) 'Cultural threat and anti-immigrant prejudice: The case of Protestants in Northern Ireland', *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, 22(2), pp. 111–124. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.1105>
- Potter, M., Bloomer, F. and Hamilton, J. (2015) 'Traveller Education: Policy and Practice in Northern Ireland', in *Tolerance and Diversity in Ireland – North and South*, pp. 74–93. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/traveller-education-policy-and-practice-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Potter, M. and Hamilton, J. (2014) 'Picking on vulnerable migrants: precarity and the mushroom industry in Northern Ireland', *Work, Employment and Society*, 28(3), pp. 390–406. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017013510760>
- Potter, M., Hamilton, J. and Bloomer, F. (2012) 'The Adequacy of Traveller Education in Northern Ireland', *Race, Ethnicity and Education*, 15(4), pp. 501–524. <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/the-adequacy-of-traveller-education-in-northern-ireland>
- Pritchard, R. and Skinner, B. (2003) 'Cross cultural partnerships between home and international students', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 6(4), pp. 323–353. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/cross-cultural-partnerships-between-home-and-international-studen-3>
- Quail, B. (2017) *The use and formation of social networks among asylum seekers and refugees in Northern Ireland*. Queen's University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/the-use-and-formation-of-social-networks-among-asylum-seekers-and> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Ray, P. (2016) 'Being Colour: Reflections on Being Indian in Belfast', *The Tangerine*, 31 December. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/being-colour-reflections-on-being-indian-in-belfast> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Reilly, J. and Niens, U. (2013) 'Ethnic minority pupils in divided societies: A critical review of theory and evidence as well as suggestions for future direction', in *Unknown Host Publication*. EERA. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/ethnic-minority-pupils-in-divided-societies-a-critical-review-of--3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Roddy, S. (2018) *Substance misuse and help-seeking amongst Polish migrants in Northern Ireland*. Ulster University. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/substance-misuse-and-help-seeking-amongst-polish-migrants-in-nort> (Accessed: 22 February 2021).
- Rooney, P. and Hassan, D. (2014) *Evaluation Report into Sport Against Racism Ireland Programmes (2012 – 2013) Partially Funded by Football for Hope*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/evaluation-report-into-sport-against-racism-ireland-programmes-20-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Schulz, M. and Taylor, L.K. (2018) 'The processes underlying the quality of contact with the primary out-group and in-group importance on support for the Syrian resettlement in a post-accord context.', *Peace and Conflict: Journal of Peace Psychology*, 24(3), pp. 306–314. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/pac0000321>
- Scrantom, K. and McLaughlin, K. (2019) 'Heroes on the Hill: A qualitative study of the psychosocial benefits of an intercultural arts programme for youth in Northern Ireland', *Journal of community and applied social psychology* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.2401>
- Selvakannu, S. (2020) 'Here and There', *Transnational Literature*, 12. Here and There — Queen's University Belfast (qub.ac.uk)
- Shirlow, P. and Bairner, A. (1998) 'Sectarianism and Racism in Sport: Soccer Fandom in Sweden and Northern Ireland', in *Football Cultures and Identities*, pp. 153–163. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/sectarianism-and-racism-in-sport-soccer-fandom-in-sweden-and-nort> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Simpson, M. (2014) "'Designed to reduce people... to complete destitution": human dignity in the active welfare state', *European Human Rights Law Review*, 2015(1), pp. 66–77.

- <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/designed-to-reduce-people-to-complete-destitution-human-dignity-i-3>
- Simpson, M., Patrick, R. and Porter, I. (2019) Northern Ireland Affairs Committee and Work and Pensions Committee joint inquiry into welfare policy in Northern Ireland: Joint submission from the Joseph Rowntree Foundation, University of York and Ulster University: Interim report on universal credit in Northern Ireland appended. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/northern-ireland-affairs-committee-and-work-and-pensions-committe> (Accessed: 11 March 2021).
- Skinner, B. (2010a) 'English as an Additional Language and initial teacher training: views and experiences from Northern Ireland', *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 36(1), pp. 75–90. <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/english-as-an-additional-language-and-initial-teacher-training-vi-3>
- Skinner, B. (2010b) 'Online discussion: can it help ease international students into British academic life?', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 14(4), pp. 335–354. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315308327866>
- Skinner, B. (2017) 'Effective teacher talk: a threshold concept in TESOL', *ELT Journal*, 71(2), pp. 150–159. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccw062>
- Skinner, B. (2019) "'Let's move on": second language trainee teachers' talk and its impact on learner interaction', *The Language Learning Journal* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2019.1642371>
- Skinner, B. and O'Toole, B. (2018) 'Minority language pupils and the curriculum: closing the achievement gap', in *Minority language pupils and the curriculum: closing the achievement gap*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/minority-language-pupils-and-the-curriculum-closing-the-achieveme> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Smiths, L.H. et al. (2019) *Social Work and Human Rights: A Practice Guide*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/social-work-and-human-rights-a-practice-guide> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Smyth, L., McClements, L. and Murphy, P. (2018) 'Engaging hard-to-reach populations in research on health in pregnancy: the value of Boal's simultaneous dramaturgy', *Arts and Health: An International Journal for Research, Policy and Practice* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17533015.2018.1555176>
- STATE (2011). Dublin: Project Arts Centre. Available at: <http://www.projectartscentre.ie> (Accessed: 29 June 2022).
- Svasek, M. (2009) 'Shared histories? Polish Migrant Experiences and the Politics of Display in Northern Ireland', in *Polish Migration to the UK in the 'New' European Union: After 2004*, pp. 129–148. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/shared-histories> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Svasek, M. (2016) 'Undoing Absence through Things: Creative Appropriation and Affective Engagement in an Indian Transnational Setting', in *Creativity in Transition: Politics and Aesthetics of Cultural Production across the Globe*, pp. 218–244. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/undoing-absence-through-things-creative-appropriation-and-affecti> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Svasek, M. (2018) 'Criss-crossing Pathways: The Indian Community Centre as Focus of Diasporic and Cross-Community Place-Making', in *Ethnographies of Movement, Sociality and Space: Place-making in the New Northern Ireland*, pp. 211–234. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/criss-crossing-pathways-the-indian-community-centre-as-focus-of-d> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Svasek, M. and Komarova, M. (2018) *Ethnographies of Movement, Sociality and Space: Place-Making in the New Northern Ireland*. Berghahn. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/ethnographies-of-movement-sociality-and-space-place-making-in-the> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Taylor, L.K. and Glen, C. (2019) 'From empathy to action: Can enhancing host-society children's empathy promote positive attitudes and prosocial behaviour toward refugees?', *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, 29(5). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.2438>

- Topping, J. (2020) *BAME PSNI Stop and Search Profile - 1st April - 30th June 2020*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/bame-psni-stop-and-search-profile-1st-april-30th-june-2020> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Vieten, U.M. (2018) 'Refugees, displacement and moving bodies:: studying loss and the language of dance'. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/refugees-displacement-and-moving-bodies-studying-loss-and-the-lan>
- Vieten, U.M. and Murphy, F. (2019) 'The Imagination of the Other in a (Post-) Sectarian Society: Asylum Seekers and Refugees in the Divided City of Belfast', *Social Inclusion*, 7(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.v7i2.1980>
- Vieten, U.M. and Murphy, F. (2021) 'Omni-present sectarianism and the life experiences of Asylum seekers and Refugees in NI'. Available at: <https://www.qub.ac.uk/Research/ethnic-minorities-ni/research/MurphyVietenblogMay21.html>
- Wallace, A., McAreavey, R. and Atkin, K. (2013) *Poverty and Ethnicity in Northern Ireland: An Evidence Review*. Joseph Rowntree Foundation. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/poverty-and-ethnicity-in-northern-ireland-an-evidence-review> (Accessed: 26 January 2021).
- Wang, S. (2017) *The Sociocultural Milieux of 'Chinese' Language Learning in Belfast: Diaspora and Difference*. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/the-sociocultural-milieux-of-chinese-language-learning-in-belfast> (Accessed: 3 February 2021).
- Waterhouse-Bradley, B. (2013) *Migrant Healthcare Access in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/migrant-healthcare-access-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 2 March 2021).
- Waterhouse-Bradley, B. (2014) *BME and Migrant Confidence in Policing in Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/bme-and-migrant-confidence-in-policing-in-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Welty, E. (2013) *Citizenship education in the global era : a comparative case study of Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland*. Queens University Belfast. Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/citizenship-education-in-the-global-era-a-comparative-case-study-> (Accessed: 18 June 2022).
- White, C. (2003) 'Race Discrimination' in 'Civil Liberties in Northern Ireland',. Committee on the Administration of Justice. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/race-discrimination-in-civil-liberties-in-northern-ireland-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- White, C. (2015) 'Race Discrimination', 'Human Rights in Northern Ireland: CAJ Handbook', pp. 329–349.
- Wilson, D. (2009) 'Platforms for a Restorative Society in Northern Ireland', December. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/platforms-for-a-restorative-society-in-northern-ireland-3> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Wilson, D. and Irwin, T. (2008) 'The "Good Relations" Agenda and The Changing Context of the Prison Officer in Northern IrelandThe Development of a Pilot Project', in *Unknown Host Publication*. Commonwealth of Learning. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/the-good-relations-agenda-and-the-changing-context-of-the-prison--2> (Accessed: 1 March 2021).
- Wu, W. (2016) 'Defining Self: Performing Chinese Identity Through Dance in Belfast', *eSharp* [Preprint], (24). Available at: <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/defining-self-performing-chinese-identity-through-dance-in-belfas>

Appendix D Question schedule for participating authors

The questions below were used for the data generation from the authors. They elected whether to reply online completely anonymously, or via an interview with me, where the transcript was pseudonymised. All questions were thus accessible prior to the interview.

About your work in this area

1. Can you write/ talk about what motivated YOU particularly to do research about/ with migrants and ethnic minorities in Northern Ireland?

2. Please discuss how such research has impacted YOU - whether your career/ your academic practice/ your thinking?

3. In terms of sustainability, we noticed from the report that very few individuals and teams are working in this area in Northern Ireland, and even fewer at postgrad level. This raises concerns about the sustainability of this area of interest into the future. Please share about the ways YOU have generated interest in such work within the academic community.

4. Not only are there few researchers conducting research at NI universities in this area; but very few seem to be NI ethnic minorities, as far as we can tell. Rather than we presume, please indicate below which YOU feels applies to you? (Closed statements)

I identify as a migrant academic (options: Strongly identify; somewhat identify; neutral; no)

I identify as a minority ethnic academic (options: Strongly identify; somewhat identify; neutral; no)

5. How you are seen in this regulatory environment?

Closed statements

I am categorised (by the UK government) as a migrant within Northern Ireland; I am categorised (by the UK government) as minority ethnic within Northern Ireland; None; Not sure.

Enablers/ constraints of such research

6. Indicate which stop, starts, success in terms of research in this area pertain to your experience. (Closed statements, with options: Yes for 2 projects or more; Yes for 1 project; No)

I have conducted such research; I have conducted such research AND published from it; I have applied for funding for such research; I have been awarded funding for such research; I have contributed to un/ self-funded research.

7. Following those projects, please indicate which apply since.

I have wanted to conduct research about migrants/ ethnic minorities in NI, but for various reasons have not done so yet; I have contributed to proposals about such research, which have not progressed to projects.

8. Indicate the institutions you have worked within when engaging in such research. (closed statements)

Queen's University Belfast; Ulster University; Independent.

7. Please let us know the period(s) to which your direct experience of research in this area relates.

Within the past 5 years; 6-10 year; 11-20 years; 20-30 years.

8. Please provide some insights into the enablements or affordances of such research across this 'life cycle'.

9. Where the research led to insights/ findings which you believed were of value for policy, practice, understandings etc in Northern Ireland, please write/ talk about the enablements for the IMPACT of such findings in NI.

10. Please provide some reflections on the constraints, barriers or problematics of such research.

11. Where the research findings were of value – what can you share about the barriers, constraints or problematics to their IMPACT in Northern Ireland?

Research culture and terrain in NI for such research

12. How do you think research – particularly about/with Northern Ireland migrants and minority ethnic people or matters - is PERCEIVED within Northern Ireland?

13. Some of the wording and topic foci within funding calls and policy construct individuals, who are categorised as migrants and minority ethnic, in certain ways. Can you provide some reflections on this, and perhaps how YOU have negotiated this in the research application/ process/ engagement/ output?

13. Any other aspects or issues you would like to highlight or share that you think is important for coming to a deeper understanding about the research culture here. ?

Appendix E Question schedule for report-and-respond discussion with research development officers

1. In what ways do you think the institution supports research that has local relevance, and researchers to do sustainable work in this area?

2. This is a marginal research area. Our scoping study (Lubit and Belluigi 2022), found 172 outputs of 123,326 items on the research repositories (Pure) of the two research-intensive universities related to this area of interest (p.22-23). This updated study saw some increase across the years, to 209 items recorded on the repositories of which they are from 159 projects (Moynihan and Belluigi 2023, p.5 figure 2). One can see increases across time (p.6 figure 4).

Can you share about the institutional research development supports for marginal research such as this? What do you think might be some of the constraints or enablements within the institution and wider than that?

3. Funding (pp.15-24). Just under half the projects acknowledged funding. However, there are clear indications about where the funding did not come from; and which projects that were funded by certain sources produced more outputs. Reflections and thoughts?

a. Figure 27 p.20 very few academic funded bodies, and outputs (19); Figure 29 – one UK funded; Figure 30 – very little EU funded

b. Figure 25 p. 18 – much funding from NGO and NI led to outputs; some projects authors really invested and produced many outputs, perhaps more about impact?

4. Nature of authorship and engagement with communities under study.

a. Figure 7 p.18 indicates their positioning, with very few influenced decision-making (powers). Show other figures in that section – many female, migrants, very few people of colour. Most authors who were Chinese/ descent for instance are only at postdoc level, and may not continue to academic positions. Reflections?

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

This project was led by **Dr Dina Zoe Belluigi**. At the time of writing, Dina was a Reader in Higher Education Studies at the School of Social Sciences, Education and Social Work (SSESW) at Queen's University Belfast (Northern Ireland). She was also a Visiting Professor at the Chair for the Critical Study of Higher Education Transformation, at Nelson Mandela (South Africa). Her research interests revolve around the agency of academic citizens, and the ways in which their critical consciousness is engendered in societies under transition. Her research has included collaborations with colleagues on higher education in South Africa, India, the United Kingdom, and this project to do with Northern Ireland.

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This report was informed by a systematic literature analysis undertaken by **Yvonne Moynihan** as a research assistant, supervised by Dr Belluigi. She also assisted with the coding and content analysis of the data generated by the study participants, and much of the data visualisation.

At the time of writing, Yvonne was a NINE DTP ESRC Scholar reading for her PhD at the School of Social Sciences, Education and Social Work (SSESW) at Queen's University Belfast. Her research explores the experiences of pupils from migrant and minority ethnic backgrounds in the different primary school types in Northern Ireland. Yvonne completed her masters in Conflict Transformation

and Social Justice at QUB and a BSc in International Development at the University College Cork.

Over the years, she has worked with various NGOs supporting inclusion and social justice in Spain, Palestine and Peru.

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We hope that readers have found this report of interest. Please visit the project site to access project updates at <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/projects/academic-research-responsiveness-to-ethnic-minorities-and-migrants>. Feedback and reflections are welcome.

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